

TechConnect
Human Tech Index

HUMAN-TECH SKILL COMPLEMENTARITY INDEX

Deliverable 2.3

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Lead Author (Org)	Laura Piscicelli (UU)
Contributing Authors (Org)	Kristoffer Pettersson (MDU)

<p>Reviewers</p>	<p>Na Fu (TCD), Anette Hallin (MDU), Christoffer Andersson (MDU), Ernestina Menasalvas (UPM), Ana Moreno (UPM), Brendan Rowan (BLU), Stephen Rigney (TCD), Anneke Schouten (UU)</p>
<p>Abstract</p>	<p>This deliverable presents the Human-Tech Skill Complementarity Index (hereafter, Human-Tech Index), developed under Work Package 2 (WP2) of the TechConnect project. The Index is designed to assess the extent to which digital technologies in healthcare, with a primary focus on hospital settings, achieve their intended use in practice. It does so by measuring the divergence between intended and actual technology use, conceptualised as the ‘affordance gap’.</p> <p>The development of the Index is grounded in a systematic umbrella review of 60 review articles and empirical findings from WP2 ethnographic case studies. Based on this combined evidence base, the Index operationalises affordance gaps through five analytical factors: Technology Characteristics; Work Practice Alignment; Trust, Safety & Governance; Implementation & Coordination Capacity; and Resource Conditions. These factors are assessed across five system levels: task, role, team, department/unit, and organisation. A key feature of the Index is its multi-source data collection and analysis design. Intended affordances are assessed by individuals involved in technology selection and implementation, whereas actual affordances are captured through end users’ experiences. The difference (affordance gaps) between these assessments constitutes the core output of the Index.</p> <p>The Human-Tech Index is structured in two stages: Quick Scan and Deep Dive. The Quick Scan comprises 25 survey items aligned with the five analytical factors across five system levels, which provides a rapid screening of affordance gaps. The Deep Dive comprises 90 additional items for targeted component-level diagnosis of areas identified as problematic during the Quick Scan stage. Overall, the Quick Scan identifies priority areas and informs the selective deployment of the Deep Dive for more detailed analysis of affordance gaps.</p> <p>This deliverable describes the conceptual foundations, methodological development and operational design of the Human-Tech Index. It also presents the Index as a conceptually grounded and empirically informed assessment tool for implementation teams, clinical leaders, and organisational stakeholders to identify, prioritise and address misalignments between intended and actual technology use in healthcare settings, thereby supporting more effective technology implementation.</p> <p>The Index is currently developed within a healthcare context, which offers particularly complex organisational work systems involving diverse professional groups, high coordination demands, regulatory pressures, and intensive technology use. Insights generated in this</p>

	<p>setting are expected to have broader analytical relevance, as the underlying logic of affordance gaps is applicable across multiple organisational contexts.</p> <p>Overall, the Index should be understood as a diagnostic and decision-support framework rather than a static measurement instrument, intended to inform iterative organisational learning.</p>
Keywords	<p>Human-Tech Index; human–technology skill complementarity; affordance gap; healthcare technology</p>

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Classified S-UE/ EU-S	EU SECRET under the Commission Decision No2015/ 444	

- * *R: Document, report (excluding the periodic and final reports)*
DEM: Demonstrator, pilot, prototype, plan designs
DEC: Websites, patent filing, press & media actions, videos, etc.
DATA: Data sets, microdata, etc
DMP: Data management plan
ETHICS: Deliverables related to ethics issues.
SECURITY: Deliverables related to security issues
OTHER: Software, technical diagram, algorithms, models, etc.

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Digital technologies are increasingly expected to improve the quality, efficiency, safety, and sustainability of healthcare systems. Across Europe and internationally, organisations are investing in electronic records, decision-support systems, artificial intelligence applications, robotics, remote monitoring tools, workflow platforms, and data infrastructures. Yet, despite these investments, many technologies do not generate the benefits initially anticipated. Systems may be technically functional but poorly integrated into daily work practices. Tools introduced to reduce workload may create new administrative burdens. Technologies designed to improve coordination may instead fragment responsibilities or remain underused. In many cases, the central challenge is not whether a technology has been implemented, but whether it functions in practice as intended.

This deliverable responds to that challenge through the development of the Human-Tech Skill Complementarity Index (hereafter, Human-Tech Index). Developed under Work Package 2 (WP2) of the TechConnect project, the Index provides a structured conceptual framework for assessing the alignment between the intended use of a digital technology and its actual use in practice. In this deliverable, any difference between these two is conceptualised as the affordance gap.

The Human-Tech Index is based on the premise that technology outcomes are relational and organisational rather than purely technical. A digital system may perform well in one setting and poorly in another depending on how it interacts with professional routines, skills, governance arrangements, leadership support, available resources, and trust in the technology. For this reason, the Index does not treat implementation problems as isolated technical failures. Instead, it examines how technologies are embedded within wider systems of work.

The conceptualisation of the Index draws on two complementary evidence sources. First, an umbrella review of 60 review articles was undertaken to identify recurring determinants of successful and unsuccessful technology use in hospital-based healthcare settings, which serve as a critical and analytically rich empirical environment for understanding complex socio-technical systems. Second, these findings were compared with empirical insights generated through WP2 case studies. Combining these sources made it possible to develop a framework that is both theoretically grounded and informed by real organisational experience.

This process resulted in a diagnostic structure organised around five analytical factors:

- Technology Characteristics
- Work Practice Alignment
- Trust, Safety and Governance
- Implementation and Coordination Capacity
- Resource Conditions

These factors are examined across five system levels:

- Task
- Role
- Team
- Department/Unit
- Organisation

Together, these dimensions enable the Index to assess where misalignments occur and how local issues may relate to broader organisational conditions.

A defining feature of the Human-Tech Index is its multi-source survey design. Intended affordances are assessed by respondents involved in technology selection, implementation, or governance, while actual affordances are assessed by end users who work with the technology in practice. Comparing these perspectives allows the Index to distinguish between technologies that are underperforming relative to clear expectations and situations where expectations themselves are unclear or contested.

The Index is structured in two complementary stages, i.e. Quick Scan and Deep Dive. The first stage, the Quick Scan, provides a concise system-wide overview. It consists of 25 assessment items reflecting the intersection of five analytical factors and five system levels. Its purpose is to identify where important affordance gaps are most likely to exist. Quick Scan items are informed by the evidence mapping developed during framework construction. Thus, each item foregrounds the determinant most strongly supported by evidence within that particular factor × level cell, rather than restating the factor in purely generic terms. The second stage, the Deep Dive, provides a more detailed diagnostic assessment. It examines the specific components underlying each factor and can be selectively deployed where the Quick Scan indicates concern. In its current conceptual form, the Deep Dive comprises of 90 component-level assessment items. This two-stage logic enables proportionate assessment. Organisations do not need to begin with a lengthy survey. Instead, they can first identify priority areas and then investigate those areas in greater detail.

The outputs of the Index are intended to support decision-making for effective technology adoption by integrating both technological and system-level perspectives (e.g. people and processes). The Index is expected to produce overall gap scores that reflect differences between intended and actual affordances of technology use in the workplace, visual heatmaps of areas of concern, and more granular component-level diagnostics. Such outputs can help organisations identify whether challenges stem primarily from design issues, workflow incompatibilities, weak governance, insufficient resources, or conflicting expectations regarding the role of the adopted technology.

It is important to note that this deliverable presents the conceptual architecture of the Human-Tech Index rather than a fully validated operational instrument. The next stage of development will involve piloting, refinement of thresholds and scoring procedures, and adaptation to settings beyond hospitals. While the current evidence base is rooted in healthcare organisations, the broader logic of the Index is intended to be transferable to other sectors in which digital technologies interact with complex systems of work.

Overall, the Human-Tech Index offers a novel and practical foundation for evaluating whether technologies deliver the value they are expected to create. By systematically comparing organisational intentions with user realities, it supports more informed implementation strategies and more effective human–technology complementarity, with potential applicability beyond healthcare and in other digitally transforming sectors.

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ABBREVIATIONS

WP	Work Package

ABOUT TECHCONNECT

TechConnect, a €3 million initiative funded by the European Union, under the Horizon Europe framework with a consortium of 9 partners, Trinity College Dublin (TCD), Mälardalen University (MDU), Polytechnic University of Madrid (UPM), Universiteit Utrecht (UU), BluSpecs, Tallaght University Hospital (TUH), Västerås Hospital (RV), Hospital Ramon y Cajal (FIBIRYCIS) and University Medical Center Utrecht (UMCU).

The TechConnect project aims to deepen the understanding of how advanced digital technologies impact human skills by focusing on Human-Tech Skill Complementarity. Through desk research, industry surveys, and case studies in healthcare, TechConnect explores how human skills and technology interact in real-world contexts. The project develops a systemic framework to address the gap between intended and actual technology use, offering practical guidelines for technology procurement, development, and training. By providing tools to enhance human-tech integration, TechConnect ambition is to boost productivity and employment across industries, driving greater alignment between technology and human skills.

1 Introduction

Digital technologies such as artificial intelligence, automation systems, analytics platforms, and digital records are increasingly introduced to improve productivity, quality, coordination, and resilience across sectors, including healthcare (Agrawal, Gans & Goldfarb 2019, 2022; Brynjolfsson & McAfee, 2014). Yet many technologies do not deliver the expected benefits once implemented in practice (Brynjolfsson, Rock & Syverson, 2021). Although technically functional, they may fit poorly with workflows, roles, governance arrangements, available skills, or organisational routines (Autor, 2015; Greenhalgh et al., 2017; Rock & Syverson, 2021). This gap between expected and realised benefits is a major challenge of digital transformation. In this deliverable, that challenge is addressed through the concept of the affordance gap, defined as the divergence between the benefits a technology is intended to provide and those actually realised in everyday use. The Human-Tech Skill Complementarity Index (Human-Tech Index) has been developed to assess these misalignments systematically and support more effective implementation.

The Human-Tech Index is a survey-based assessment tool designed to evaluate the degree of alignment between digital technologies and the work practices in which they are embedded. It provides a structured way to identify where affordance gaps occur, how severe they are, and which organisational conditions may help explain them.

The proposed Index uses a multi-source survey design involving two respondent groups. Individuals involved in technology selection, implementation, or governance assess what the technology is intended to achieve, while end users assess what it actually enables in practice. Comparing these perspectives helps identify where affordance gaps may exist.

The instrument also follows a two-stage diagnostic logic consisting of the Quick Scan and the Deep Dive. The Quick Scan provides a concise overview of where misalignments are most likely to occur across analytical factors and system levels. Where clearer diagnosis is required, the Deep Dive offers a more detailed examination of the underlying causes of those gaps. Together, these stages enable both rapid screening and more targeted analysis.

The Index draws on evidence from a systematic umbrella review of published review studies in healthcare settings and empirical insights from WP2 case studies conducted in hospitals. This combined evidence base was used to identify recurring factors shaping human-technology complementarity and to translate these into a structured measurement framework.

The purpose of this deliverable is to present the conceptual architecture of the Human-Tech Index. It sets out the theoretical rationale, evidence base, development methodology, proposed survey logic, and intended analytical outputs. It does not yet present a fully validated operational tool. Further piloting and refinement are expected in subsequent phases of work.

Although the current evidence base is rooted in hospital settings, the broader ambition of the Human-Tech Index is wider. Healthcare was selected as the primary empirical setting for WP2. This choice was deliberate. Hospital systems provide a particularly valuable analytical environment because they combine organisational complexity, strong regulatory requirements, intensive knowledge work, diverse occupational groups, time-critical decision-making, and rapidly expanding use of digital technologies (Cresswell & Sheikh, 2013; Greenhalgh et al., 2017). Hospitals therefore offer a representative microcosm in which broader dynamics of digital transformation can be observed. The healthcare sector also contains many of the coordination, trust, skills, governance, and workflow challenges that arise in other sectors. Insights generated through the healthcare case studies can therefore inform wider cross-sector learning and future adaptation of the Human-Tech Index beyond hospital settings. The underlying logic of comparing expected and realised technology benefits across organisational systems is likely to be relevant in sectors beyond healthcare.

The remainder of this deliverable is structured as follows. Section 2 presents the conceptual foundations of the Index, including the rationale for its multi-factor and multi-level design. Section 3 explains how these concepts were developed from the evidence base and translated into the proposed measurement framework. Section 4 sets out the survey architecture, scoring logic, and expected outputs. Section 5 concludes with methodological reflections, limitations, and priorities for future development.

2 Conceptual Foundations of the Human-Tech Index

2.1 Why a New Assessment Framework is Needed

The rapid expansion of digital technologies has generated substantial interest in how organisations can successfully adopt and use new tools. In response, a wide range of models and frameworks have emerged to assess technology implementation. These include technology acceptance models, usability frameworks, readiness assessments, implementation science frameworks, and digital maturity tools (Damschroder et al., 2009; Venkatesh et al., 2003; Weiner et al., 2008).

Such approaches have made important contributions. They have improved understanding of how perceptions of usefulness and ease of use shape adoption decisions (Venkatesh et al., 2003); how organisational readiness influences implementation (Weiner et al., 2008); and how technical design affects user interaction (Nielsen, 1993). However, many existing approaches focus primarily on one dimension of the challenge rather than the relationship between them.

For example, acceptance models often concentrate on user attitudes and behavioural intentions. Maturity tools may assess infrastructure and governance capacity. Usability instruments typically focus on interface quality and user interaction. Implementation frameworks may examine change processes, stakeholder engagement, or contextual barriers. Each of these perspectives is valuable, but none fully captures whether a technology ultimately delivers the practical value it was expected to create across multiple organisational levels.

In healthcare settings, this limitation is particularly important. Hospitals are complex socio-technical environments in which technologies interact with professional autonomy, safety requirements, time pressures, coordination needs, regulatory obligations, and diverse occupational groups (Cresswell & Sheikh, 2013; Greenhalgh et al., 2017). A technology may be positively received by some actors and resisted by others; may improve one workflow while disrupting another; or may function effectively at task level while generating tensions at team or organisational level.

The Human-Tech Index has been developed to address this gap. Rather than asking only whether users accept a technology, whether implementation followed good practice, or whether infrastructure is in place, it asks a more integrative question: *To what extent does the technology deliver the affordances it was expected to provide in real organisational practice?*

This question shifts attention from adoption alone to realised complementarity between technology and human work systems.

2.2 The Concept of the Affordance Gap

The Human-Tech Index is grounded in the concept of technological affordances (Leonardi, 2011). In broad terms, affordances refer to the possibilities for action that a technology enables in

relation to its use (see also: D1.1 Human-Tech Skill Complementarity Conceptual Framework Development; D2.2 Human-Tech Skill Complementarity Conceptual Framework II). A digital tool is commonly designed to afford faster information access, automated calculations, improved communication, standardisation of processes, or better monitoring of operations. However, such possibilities are not automatically realised simply because the technology exists.

Affordances depend on the way the technology is used. The same technology may thus generate different outcomes depending on which skills are mobilized, on how the activity connects in a workflow, how leadership supports the use of technology, the extent to which the technology is interoperable with other systems, and how its use fits local organisational norms. As a result, intended affordances and actual affordances may diverge.

In this deliverable, the affordance gap (Figure 1) refers to the difference between:

- **Intended affordances:** what the technology is expected to provide or produce by those responsible for selecting, designing, commissioning, or implementing it; and
- **Actual affordances:** what the technology actually provides or produces as it is used in daily work.

Figure 1. Affordance gap

This distinction is analytically useful because it recognises that implementation success is not binary. Technologies are rarely simply “successful” or “failed”. Instead, they may realise some intended affordances while falling short on others.

For example:

- A scheduling platform may reduce manual planning time but increase coordination complexity across teams.
- A clinical AI tool may improve consistency of recommendations but be used selectively because outputs are not trusted.
- A digital record system may centralise information but create additional data-entry burden for frontline staff.

The Human-Tech Index is designed to make such patterns visible in a structured and comparable way.

2.3 A Multi-Level Perspective on Human-Technology Complementarity

Affordance gaps can emerge at different levels of organisational life (Klein & Kozlowski, 2000). Some problems are highly localised, while others reflect broader structural conditions. For this reason, the Human-Tech Index adopts a multi-level perspective consisting of five system levels (see also D1.1 Human-Tech Skill Complementarity Conceptual Framework Development; D2.2 Human-Tech Skill Complementarity Conceptual Framework II):

- **Task level:** specific activities, routines, and immediate work processes, focusing on how humans and technology interact in the execution of concrete tasks and how technology reshapes the sequencing, effort, and conduct of day-to-day work.
- **Role level:** responsibilities, autonomy, and professional functions, referring to how technology affects the content and boundaries of professional roles beyond individual tasks, including changes in expertise, decision-making authority, and job scope.
- **Team level:** collaboration, coordination, and shared workflows, capturing how technology mediates interaction among professionals working together and influences communication patterns, interdependencies, and collective task performance.
- **Department/Unit level:** local management, resources, and service organisation, referring to how technology shapes the structuring and delivery of services within organisational sub-units, including workflow design, resource allocation, and operational coordination.
- **Organisation level:** strategy, governance, infrastructure, and institutional direction, focusing on how technology interacts with organisational vision and governance and contributes to broader changes in strategy, institutional priorities, and organisational design (Figure 2).

Figure 2. System levels

This structure recognises that problems observed in one area may originate elsewhere. For example, a task-level burden may reflect weak system integration. Team-level coordination issues

may stem from unclear governance. Organisation-level strategy may fail because professional roles were insufficiently considered during implementation.

A multi-level approach therefore improves diagnosis by locating issues more precisely and by highlighting interdependencies across the system. How these five levels are operationalised within the survey instrument is described later in Section 4.

2.4 Analytical Factors Shaping Affordance Realisation

Based on the evidence review and case-study analysis (D2.2 Human-Tech Skill Complementarity Conceptual Framework II), the Human-Tech Index organises assessment around five analytical factors that recurrently shape whether technologies deliver intended affordances. These factors also correspond to well-known construct families in the socio-technical and implementation literature (Lee & See, 2004; Nielsen, 1993; Nilsen, 2015; Venkatesh et al., 2003).

- **Technology Characteristics:** This factor concerns the properties of the technology itself, including usability, reliability, interoperability, and perceived usefulness. Even well-supported implementation processes may struggle if the tool is difficult to use or poorly integrated with existing systems.
- **Work Practice Alignment:** This factor concerns the fit between the technology and existing workflows, professional routines, responsibilities, and service processes. Technologies that conflict with how work is actually organised may create resistance or inefficiency.
- **Trust, Safety and Governance:** This factor captures confidence in outputs, transparency of system functioning, data protection, accountability arrangements, and perceived safety. Trust is especially important where technologies influence decisions or sensitive data flows.
- **Implementation and Coordination Capacity:** This factor concerns leadership support, training, communication, change management, stakeholder engagement, and coordination during deployment. Even strong technologies may underperform if implementation capacity is weak.
- **Resource Conditions:** This factor captures the material and organisational resources required for effective use, including time, staffing, technical support, infrastructure, and financial capacity.

Together, these five factors provide a balanced framework that includes technical, organisational, relational, and practical determinants of technology performance. Their empirical derivation, coding logic, and refinement through the literature review and case studies are explained in Section 3.

2.5 Core Design Logic of the Human-Tech Index

The Human-Tech Index combines the five analytical factors and five system levels into a structured diagnostic matrix. This enables users to assess not only whether a gap exists, but also:

- where the gap is located.
- which system levels and factors are implicated.
- whether gaps are concentrated or systemic.
- what targeted interventions are most effective.

For example, if the affordance gaps are concentrated in Technology Characteristics across all levels, issues such as usability or interface design may require attention. If gaps cluster around Work Practice Alignment at team and role level, workflow redesign or stronger professional engagement may be more appropriate. If implementation actors disagree strongly about intended affordances, governance clarification may be needed before operational fixes are pursued.

The Index is therefore intended not merely as a measurement device, but as a structured learning framework that helps organisations reflect on how technologies interact with systems of work. In practical terms, this is achieved through a two-stage survey process consisting of a Quick Scan screening stage and a targeted Deep Dive diagnostic stage.

2.6 Scope of the Deliverable

This deliverable presents the conceptual foundations of the Human-Tech Index and the logic underlying its proposed structure. The current version should be understood as a prototype framework informed by available evidence rather than a final validated instrument. In the next phases of the TechConnect project, the Index will be further developed and tested (D3.3 Human-Tech Skill Complementarity Strengthening Model).

The Index's immediate empirical grounding lies in hospital settings, reflecting the focus of the literature review and WP2 case studies. However, the conceptual principles underlying the Index are not inherently sector specific. Following further testing and refinement, the framework may be adaptable to other organisational environments in which digital technologies reshape human work practices. This broader transfer and practical application will be supported in later project outputs, including D4.2 Validated TechConnect Stakeholder Toolkit and D5.2 Exploitation Roadmap.

3 Evidence Base and Index Development Process

The Human-Tech Index was developed through a structured multi-stage process that combined evidence synthesis with empirical refinement. The aim was to ensure that the proposed framework is both conceptually grounded and practically relevant. Rather than deriving the Human-Tech Index from a single theoretical model or from one case context alone, the development process integrated insights from published scientific research with observations from real organisational settings.

Two principal evidence sources were used to construct the conceptual framework later translated into the survey instrument:

- a systematic ‘umbrella review’ of review literature relating to digital technologies in hospital settings; and
- empirical insights generated through WP2 case studies (D2.2 Systems Analysis).

The combination of these sources enabled the project to identify recurring determinants of Human-Tech Complementarity while also testing whether those determinants were observable in practice.

3.1 Overview of Methodology

The development of the Human-Tech Index followed four sequential stages (Figure 3), moving from evidence identification to eventual survey design:

1. Evidence identification through an umbrella review of review studies.
2. Coding and synthesis of determinants shaping technology use and implementation.
3. Empirical refinement using WP2 case-study findings.
4. Translation into an assessment architecture comprising analytical factors, system levels, survey logic, and scoring principles.

Figure 3. Four-stage development process of the Human-Tech Index

This staged approach was chosen because no single source of evidence was sufficient on its own. Review studies offer breadth and cumulative insight, while case studies provide contextual depth and practical realism. Combining both strengthens conceptual robustness.

3.2 Stage 1: Umbrella Review of Existing Evidence

3.2.1 Rationale

An umbrella review (Aromataris et al. 2015, 2020) was undertaken to identify the most consistently reported factors shaping the successful use of digital technologies in hospital settings. An umbrella review synthesises evidence from existing review studies rather than only from individual primary studies. This approach was considered appropriate for three reasons. First, the field of digital health implementation is already extensive and fragmented across multiple technologies and disciplines. Second, review studies often consolidate findings across many empirical settings, making them useful for identifying recurrent themes. Third, an umbrella review supports higher-level framework development by drawing on already synthesised evidence.

3.2.2 Search Strategy

The review was conducted using a structured search of the Scopus database. Search terms combined concepts relating to:

- digital technologies (e.g. AI, robotics, digital platforms).
- healthcare or hospital settings.
- professionals or staff users.
- work practices, routines, tasks, or organisational processes; and
- determinants such as barriers, enablers, drivers, or influencing factors.

The full query string is provided below:

(TITLE-ABS-KEY (("digital technolog" OR "medical technolog*" OR "artificial intelligence" OR AI OR "machine learning" OR robotic* OR "augmented reality" OR "virtual reality" OR "digital platform*") AND (interaction* OR augmentation OR automation OR complementarity OR collaboration OR adoption OR acceptance OR implementation OR introduction OR "technology use")) AND TITLE-ABS-KEY (staff* OR personnel* OR worker* OR nurse* OR physician* OR doctor* OR clinician* OR "healthcare worker*" OR "medical staff*" OR "healthcare professional*") AND TITLE-ABS-KEY (hospital* OR healthcare OR "acute care" OR "clinical setting*") AND TITLE-ABS-KEY (workflow* OR "work practice*" OR routine* OR "work process*" OR skill* OR task* OR role* OR team* OR department* OR organisational* OR organisational*) AND TITLE-ABS-KEY (factor* OR determinant* OR enabler* OR barrier* OR driver* OR indicator*)) AND (LIMIT-TO (DOCTYPE,"ar") OR LIMIT-TO (DOCTYPE,"re")) AND (LIMIT-TO (LANGUAGE,"English")))*

Only English-language journal articles classified as reviews were included. The search was conducted on 18 November 2025 and returned 302 review articles.

3.2.3 Screening and Article Selection

The search yielded a broad pool of potentially relevant publications. Records were screened in stages:

- title and abstract screening for relevance (n=302).
- full-text review against inclusion criteria (n=91).
- final inclusion of studies focused on organisational use of digital technologies by healthcare professionals (n=60).

Studies focused exclusively on patients, purely technical system design, or non-hospital contexts without transferable relevance were excluded.

The final review corpus comprised 60 review articles (no. source studies included in the reviews = 1318).

3.2.4 Scope of the Evidence Base

The included studies covered a wide range of technologies, including:

- electronic health records.
- clinical decision-support systems.
- artificial intelligence tools.
- telehealth and remote monitoring systems.
- robotic systems.
- digital workflow platforms; and
- integrated information systems.

This breadth was valuable because the Human-Tech Index is intended to assess common organisational dynamics across technologies rather than one tool type only (see also: D1.3 Case Study Fiche).

3.3 Stage 2: Coding and Synthesis of Review Findings

3.3.1 Analytical Approach

The selected review studies were analysed using structured qualitative content analysis (Krippendorff, 2018; Neuendorf, 2017). This method is commonly used where the objective is to identify recurring themes, categories, and relationships across textual evidence.

The coding process combined:

- deductive logic, informed by existing socio-technical and implementation literature; and
- inductive logic, allowing new themes to emerge from the reviewed evidence.

This hybrid approach avoided imposing an overly rigid pre-existing framework while still enabling systematic comparison across studies. All extracted findings and coding iterations were managed in Microsoft Excel, which was used to organise source material, assign codes, compare categories, and maintain an audit trail across coding rounds.

3.3.2 First-Cycle Coding

In the first cycle, extracted findings from each review were coded line-by-line for reported determinants influencing technology outcomes. These determinants included both enabling and constraining conditions. Coding focused on statements describing conditions that shaped whether technologies achieved intended outcomes in practice, including technical, organisational, professional, and contextual influences.

Examples included:

- lack of interoperability.
- inadequate training.
- workflow disruption.
- improved information access.
- leadership support.
- mistrust of algorithms.
- insufficient staffing.
- professional resistance.

At this stage, coding remained close to the language used in the source material. Where the reviewed text made the locus of influence sufficiently clear, codes were also provisionally linked to one or more system levels (task, role, team, department/unit, organisation). This level coding was based on whether the determinant primarily concerned immediate work activities, professional responsibilities, collaborative practices, local service organisation, or wider organisational structures (Table 1).

This open coding stage generated more than 400 initial factor codes across the 60 included reviews, capturing barriers and enablers at varying levels of specificity. Variables relating to user characteristics (e.g. age, profession, digital literacy, prior experience, attitudes toward technology) were also identified during first-cycle coding. These were retained as contextual descriptors and potential explanatory variables but were provisionally distinguished from system-level determinants because they describe variation between users rather than organisational conditions that can be directly redesigned through implementation strategy.

Table 1 Example of first-cycle coding and provisional system level assignment

Abbas et al. (2025, p.15):	Initial codes	Level
<i>“Although many models demonstrate technical efficacy in controlled settings, practical adoption in clinical settings depends on how well they align with clinicians’ workflows, interpretive expectations, and decision-making processes.”</i>	Alignment with clinicians’ workflows	Task
	Performance expectancy	Task
	Alignment with decision-making processes	Task; Role

3.3.3 Second-Cycle Coding

In the second cycle, related first-order codes were grouped into broader conceptual categories. For example:

- usability, interface burden, and navigation problems were grouped under Technology Characteristics.
- workflow fit, role clarity, and burden redistribution were grouped under Work Practice Alignment.
- trust, explainability, privacy, and accountability were grouped under Trust, Safety and Governance.

This stage moved from descriptive coding toward analytical abstraction. Through multiple iterative rounds of comparison and consolidation, the coding framework progressed from more than 400 initial determinant codes to five broader analytical categories. Code merging was guided by standard qualitative synthesis principles of conceptual similarity, explanatory relevance, and non-duplication (Krippendorff, 2018; Neuendorf, 2017). Codes were clustered where they referred to substantively similar mechanisms (e.g. training deficits, lack of onboarding, and insufficient skill preparation), while conceptually distinct themes were retained separately. Categories were refined until they demonstrated internal coherence, clear boundaries from adjacent categories, and relevance across multiple studies.

The provisional level assignments from first-cycle coding were subsequently reviewed and refined during second-cycle analysis. Each code and emerging component was confirmed or reassigned to one or more system levels according to the primary locus at which the determinant operated. Determinants affecting execution of immediate work activities were coded at task level; those relating to responsibilities, autonomy, or professional expectations at role level; those concerning collaboration and communication at team level; those linked to local management or service organisation at department/unit level; and those relating to strategy, governance, infrastructure, or organisation-wide resources at organisational level. Where determinants operated across multiple levels, multi-level coding was permitted.

Within the five higher-order factors, a further set of eighteen components was identified to preserve analytical detail while maintaining a parsimonious overall structure. These components represent recurrent sub-dimensions that can be operationalised within the Human-Tech Index.

3.3.4 Reliability and Consensus Process

To strengthen rigour, coding and category development were reviewed iteratively by multiple researchers. Differences in interpretation were discussed until consensus was reached. Category definitions were refined during this process to improve clarity, distinctiveness, and internal coherence.

The purpose was not to generate statistically fixed categories, but to ensure that the framework reflected transparent and defensible judgement. Particular attention was given to whether candidate categories were sufficiently actionable for later measurement and whether they could plausibly inform intervention priorities in organisational settings.

3.3.5 Outcome of the Review Coding

The coding process identified a stable set of recurring determinants that could be organised into five higher-order analytical factors and a more detailed set of eighteen underlying components. These became the conceptual basis of the Human-Tech Index (Figure 4).

Figure 4: Coding tree showing the factors and components of human–technology affordance gaps identified through umbrella review.

Note: Numbers indicate the frequency with which each concept appeared across the reviewed papers.

User characteristics were not excluded from the framework; instead, they are treated as contextual variables collected through the background section of the survey and used during analysis rather than incorporated into the core Index dimensions themselves. In practice, this means they can be used to compare results across professions, seniority levels, departments, prior experience with the technology, or levels of digital confidence. This allows analysts to examine whether the same technology creates different affordance gaps for different user groups.

This distinction helps keep the Index focused on organisational and technological conditions that can potentially be changed through design, training, coordination, or resource allocation, while still recognising meaningful variation between users. It also improves interpretation of affordance gaps by showing for whom, and under which circumstances, misalignments are greatest, rather than treating all users as a homogeneous group.

3.4 Stage 3: Empirical Refinement through WP2 Case Studies

3.4.1 Role of the Case Studies

The umbrella review provided breadth, but literature alone cannot fully capture how technologies function in real organisational settings. For this reason, findings were refined using WP2 case studies undertaken within TechConnect.

These case studies generated qualitative insights into technology use in practice, including how technologies were interpreted, adapted, resisted, or integrated into everyday routines. The empirical material used at this stage consisted of a cross-case synthesis document summarising the main affordance gap types and their associated system level identified across WP2 cases. These gap types described recurring mismatches between intended and actual technology use observed in practice.

3.4.2 Refinement Process

Case-study material was analysed using the same hybrid deductive–inductive logic applied in the umbrella review. Deductively, the preliminary five-factor and component framework derived from the literature was used as an initial coding template. Inductively, the case material was examined for new distinctions, contextual nuances, or multi-level interactions not sufficiently captured in the literature-based structure.

Case-study material (i.e. the cross-case synthesis document) was used in three ways:

- to confirm whether factors identified in the literature were visible in practice.
- to refine definitions where literature categories were too abstract or broad.
- to identify where issues emerged differently across system levels.

Each affordance gap type identified in the cross-case synthesis was mapped to one or more provisional factors and components (Figure 2). Where a gap could not be adequately represented, component definitions were revisited and adjusted. In practice, all empirically

future applications. A factor commonly identified at one level in earlier studies may emerge at another level depending on organisational context, technology type, or implementation stage.

Table 2 therefore serves two purposes. First, it documents where factors and components were most clearly evidenced during framework development. Second, it informs item wording in the Quick Scan. Because each Quick Scan cell contains only one item, the wording gives greater emphasis to the component(s) most strongly associated with that factor × level combination in the evidence base. For example, organisational Resource Conditions may emphasise cost or infrastructure, whereas another cell may foreground trust or workflow fit. Where prior evidence was limited, items were still retained to preserve the complete 5 × 5 framework, using conceptually plausible wording for that level.

Table 2 - Evidence mapping – factors and components by source.

Note: Lit = Literature review; CS = WP2 case studies

Factor	Component	Task	Role	Team	Dept/Unit	Org.
Technology characteristics	Usability	Lit	CS			
	Usefulness	Lit	CS	Lit	CS	
	Technical integration		CS		CS	Lit
Work Practice Alignment	Workflow integration			CS	CS	Lit
	Workload and strain		Lit	CS		
	Roles, responsibilities, and integrity		Lit	CS	Lit	CS
	Quality and efficiency of care		Lit			
	Collaboration			Lit	CS	
Trust, Safety & Governance	Data quality (algorithmic bias and fairness)					Lit
	Transparency		Lit			
	Safety and reliability				CS	CS
	Data privacy and governance					Lit
	Legal frameworks and accountability		CS			Lit
Implementation & Coordination Capacity	Organisational readiness and engagement		CS		CS	Lit
	Training and support		Lit	CS	CS	CS
	Social influence		Lit	Lit	Lit	
Resource Conditions	Cost and financial considerations			CS	CS	Lit
	Structural and operational resources		CS	CS	CS	Lit

3.5 Final Analytical Framework

The combined review and case-study process resulted in a final framework structured around five analytical factors and five system levels.

Five Analytical Factors

- Technology Characteristics
- Work Practice Alignment
- Trust, Safety and Governance
- Implementation and Coordination Capacity
- Resource Conditions

Five System Levels

- Task
- Role
- Team
- Department/Unit
- Organisation

The resulting framework represents an integrated synthesis rather than a literature-only taxonomy. Factor labels, component boundaries, and level definitions were refined iteratively using evidence from both stages (Table 3). The literature review provided breadth, recurrence and conceptual consistency across studies, while the case studies contributed contextual specificity, practical relevance, and evidence of cross-level interactions.

All final factors and components can be traced back to the combined evidence base, strengthening transparency in how the Index was constructed.

Table 3: Human-Tech Index factors – descriptions and constituent components

Factor	Description	Components
Technology Characteristics	The usability, perceived usefulness, and integration capacity of the technology as a (clinical) tool	Usability; Usefulness; System integration
Work Practice Alignment	The alignment of the technology with (clinical) workflows, professional roles, and everyday practices	Workflow integration; Workload and strain; Roles, responsibilities, and integrity; Quality and efficiency of care; Collaboration
Trust, Safety & Governance	Confidence in the reliability, safety, transparency, and ethical governance of the technology	Data quality (algorithmic bias and fairness); Transparency; Safety and reliability; Data privacy and governance; Legal frameworks and accountability
Implementation & Coordination Capacity	Organisational support, leadership, and coordination for technology adoption	Organisational readiness and engagement; Training and support; Social influence

Resource Conditions	The financial, technical, and infrastructural resources required for implementation and sustained use	Cost and financial considerations; Structural and operational resources
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Underlying Components

Each factor is further supported by more specific components that can be explored through the Deep Dive stage of the Index. Examples include:

- usability.
- interoperability.
- workload impact.
- collaboration quality.
- trust in outputs.
- training adequacy.
- leadership support.
- infrastructure sufficiency.

This layered structure allows both concise overview assessment and more granular diagnosis. Together, the five factors and eighteen components form the measurement architecture of the Human-Tech Index, with each component capable of being examined across multiple system levels where relevant.

Table 4: Human-Tech Index components – descriptions

Factor	Component	Description
Technology characteristics	Usability	Ease of interaction with the system, including interface design, intuitiveness, and cognitive effort required.
	Usefulness	Perceived value in achieving goals and improving performance or outcomes.
	Technical integration	Compatibility and interoperability with existing digital systems and data infrastructure.
Work Practice Alignment	Workflow integration	How well the technology fits into existing processes and routines without causing disruption
	Workload and strain	The impact of technology use on effort, mental load, and practical demands.
	Roles, responsibilities, and integrity	Influence on autonomy, accountability, and professional judgment.
	Quality and efficiency of care	Effect on accuracy, effectiveness, and timeliness of outcomes.
	Collaboration	Ability to support coordination, communication, and shared understanding among people.
Trust, Safety & Governance	Data quality (algorithmic bias and fairness)	Accuracy, reliability, consistency, and fairness of outputs.
	Transparency	Clarity and interpretability of outputs and system processes.
	Safety and reliability	Consistency, error likelihood, and risk mitigation associated with the system.
	Data privacy and governance	Protection, ethical use, and compliance of data management.

	Legal frameworks and accountability	Clarity and adequacy of legal and regulatory frameworks in assigning responsibility, liability, and accountability for outcomes involving the technology.
Implementation & Coordination Capacity	Organisational readiness and engagement	The degree of leadership commitment, stakeholder buy-in, and preparedness for technology adoption.
	Training and support	Availability and quality of guidance, educational and (technical) assistance for effective use.
	Social influence	Effects of peer support, champions, and prevailing norms on adoption and engagement.
Resource Conditions	Cost and financial considerations	Financial viability and sustainability of acquiring, implementing, and maintaining the technology.
	Structural and operational resources	Availability of necessary infrastructure, equipment, and personnel for effective use.

3.6 Translation from Evidence to Index Design

The final development stage involved translating the analytical framework into an operational assessment model. Four design choices were especially important:

- **Comparative Measurement:** The Index compares intended and actual affordances rather than measuring only attitudes, satisfaction or implementation quality.
- **Multi-Source Assessment:** Different respondent groups assess intended expectations and actual experience, reducing reliance on a single perspective.
- **Tiered Depth:** A short system-wide screening stage is complemented by deeper targeted diagnosis where needed.
- **Evidence-Guided Item Framing:** Survey item wording is informed by the evidence mapping in Table 2. In the Deep Dive, each component can be assessed across levels. In the Quick Scan, where one item represents an entire factor x level cell, wording prioritises the most relevant component(s) identified during framework development.

These choices distinguish the Human-Tech Index from many existing tools that focus on only one dimension of technology implementation.

4 Operationalisation of the Human-Tech Index

4.1 Overview

The Human-Tech Index is operationalised as a structured survey-based assessment framework designed to compare intended and actual affordances of digital technologies. It is conceived as a modular framework, allowing organisations to apply the Quick Scan or extend the assessment through the Deep Dive depending on analytical needs and available resources.

Survey items were systematically derived from the final analytical framework (five factors × five system levels × eighteen components), ensuring traceability from evidence synthesis to proposed measurement instrument (Appendix 1-4). At the conceptual stage, items are linked to clearly defined analytical domains rather than treated as standalone survey questions. Each item maps to a specific factor–level–component configuration, preserving conceptual consistency across the framework.

Its design reflects three principles:

- proportionality (short initial assessment, deeper follow-up where needed).
- comparability (standardised scoring across dimensions).
- practical usability (clear outputs for decision-making).

The Index therefore uses a two-stage architecture supported by a multi-source survey design.

4.2 Multi-Source Survey Design

A defining feature of the Index is that it collects information from more than one respondent group, adopting a so-called multi-source survey design (Van Quaquebeke et al., 2022). This design was chosen because affordance gaps concern the relationship between expectations and lived experience; these perspectives are unlikely to be captured adequately through a single respondent source.

Respondent Group 1: Tech Selection & Implementation Panel

These may include individuals involved in:

- procurement.
- implementation leadership.
- governance.
- digital transformation roles.
- departmental management.

Their responses are used to assess intended affordances: what the technology is expected to achieve.

Respondent Group 2: End Users

These are professionals who interact with the technology in daily work.

Their responses are used to assess actual affordances: what the technology actually enables in practice.

Why This Matters

The Human-Tech Index distinguishes between strategic expectations and operational experience. This makes it possible to identify whether observed problems reflect:

- underperformance relative to clear goals; or
- disagreement about what the technology was supposed to achieve.

For each survey item, wording is kept structurally aligned across respondent groups, with only the referent perspective (intended vs actual affordance) adapted. This supports measurement comparability and enables direct comparison between expectation and experience at item level.

4.2.1 Survey Item Development

Survey items were developed through a structured translation process from the final analytical framework (Section 3.5). Each of the five analytical factors and eighteen components was operationalised into survey statements across the five system levels (task, role, team, department/unit, organisation) (see Appendix 1-4).

In the Quick Scan, the component structure is condensed into factor-by-level items (factor x level) whose wording is informed by the evidence mapping in Table 2 (see Section 4.3.1). In the Deep Dive this produces a component-by-level (component x level) matrix. This distinction reflects the different purposes of the two stages: breadth in the Quick Scan and depth in the Deep Dive.

Item formulation followed a standardised template. Respondents are asked to rate the extent to which a given affordance (e.g. usability, workflow integration, trust) is expected to be achieved (intended condition) or is experienced in practice (actual condition) at a specific system level.

In the Deep Dive, each of the eighteen components is assessed across the five system levels, with wording varying mainly by level referent (for example, “everyday work tasks” versus “your professional role”). In the Quick Scan, where one item must represent a whole factor at a given level, wording draws on the component(s) most strongly supported by the evidence base for that factor x level cell (in Table 2). This preserves conceptual traceability while keeping the instrument concise.

4.2.2 Response Scaling

All items are measured using a 5-point Likert-type scale ranging from 1 = “very low extent” to 5 = “very high extent”, with an additional “Not Applicable/Don’t Know” option where relevant. This format was selected because it is widely used in organisational and implementation research, is readily interpretable for mixed stakeholder groups, and is suitable for comparative gap analysis across groups and system levels (Boone & Boone, 2012; Carifio & Perla, 2008).

To ensure comparability across intended and actual versions, identical scale anchors are used for both respondent groups.

4.3 Two-Stage Assessment Structure

The Index combines two complementary stages. Each Quick Scan item corresponds to a factor–level intersection, while Deep Dive items operationalise the component structure within those same intersections. The two stages are intended to be sequential rather than competing instruments: the Quick Scan identifies where closer attention is warranted, and the Deep Dive helps explain why.

4.3.1 Stage 1: Quick Scan

The Quick Scan is the entry point to the Index. It provides a concise system-wide overview and consists of 25 assessment cells formed by 5 analytical factors × 5 system levels. Its purpose is to identify where affordance gaps are most likely to exist.

The Quick Scan is designed for routine organisational use and to minimise respondent burden. Because each cell is represented by a single item, item content prioritises the component(s) most strongly supported by the evidence base for that factor–level combination. In practice, items emphasise themes that were most salient in the literature review and WP2 case studies. For example, where prior evidence at team level highlighted interoperability or coordination, these themes inform the corresponding item.

Where Table 2 shows limited or no prior evidence for a factor at a given level, the Quick Scan still retains an item in order to preserve the complete 5 × 5 framework. In such cases, the item is anchored in the most plausible proximal mechanism through which the factor may operate at that level. This reflects a deliberate methodological choice: absence of prior evidence is not treated as evidence of absence in future implementation contexts. This approach maintains coverage, preserves comparability across the matrix, and keeps respondent burden aligned with the purpose of a short initial scan.

Illustrative Quick Scan instruments for the Tech Selection & Implementation Panel and End Users are provided in Appendix 1 and Appendix 2 respectively.

4.3.2 Stage 2: Deep Dive

The Deep Dive provides more detailed diagnosis following the Quick Scan. It examines the underlying components associated with the five analytical factors across relevant system levels. In its current conceptual form, this comprises up to 90 items.

The Deep Dive is not intended to be deployed universally. Rather, it is selectively activated where Quick Scan findings indicate concern or where organisations require more detailed analysis. This staged logic ensures analytical depth without unnecessary survey length. It also improves feasibility by concentrating respondent effort where the potential value of further diagnosis is greatest.

Illustrative Deep Dive instruments for the Tech Selection & Implementation Panel and End Users panel are provided in Appendix 3 and Appendix 4 respectively.

4.4 Scoring Logic and Interpretation

The Human-Tech Index is designed to generate interpretable diagnostic information rather than a single abstract composite score. Its scoring logic therefore focuses on comparing perspectives, identifying areas of misalignment, and supporting organisational reflection.

4.4.1 Core Affordance Gap Calculation

For each assessable unit, the Index compares the rating provided by respondents assessing intended affordances with the rating provided by respondents assessing actual affordances (Parasuraman et al., 1988).

$$\textit{Affordance Gap} = \textit{Intended Affordance Score} - \textit{Actual Affordance Score}$$

A positive score indicates that the technology is perceived to deliver less in practice than expected. A score close to zero indicates relative alignment. Negative values may indicate that practice exceeds original expectations, although such findings should be interpreted carefully.

This principle is applied consistently across both stages:

- in the Quick Scan, for factor × system-level units.
- in the Deep Dive, for component × system-level units.

4.4.2 Aggregation of Intended Affordances

Because intended affordances are typically assessed by a smaller group of implementation actors, their responses are aggregated into a reference score.

At the current conceptual stage, based on previous research (Boone & Boone, 2012; Jamieson, 2004), the median is proposed as the preferred aggregation statistic of intended affordances because it:

- is robust to outliers.
- is appropriate for smaller panels.
- reduces undue influence of extreme ratings.
- is readily interpretable.

Alternative aggregation procedures may be examined during later empirical testing.

4.4.3 Aggregation of Actual Affordances

Ratings of actual affordances are usually obtained from a broader group of end users. These responses may be summarised using the mean or median, depending on sample size and distribution.

Because actual use may differ across professions, departments, or sites, subgroup analysis is expected to be particularly informative.

4.4.4 Traffic-Light Interpretation Framework

To support practical use, gap scores may be translated into indicative interpretation bands (Table 5).

Table 5: Gap scores interpretation bands

Gap Magnitude	Indicative Meaning	Suggested Response
Low (e.g. gap < 2)	Broad alignment	Monitor
Moderate (e.g. gap ≥ 2 and < 3)	Emerging mismatch	Investigate
High (e.g. gap ≥ 3)	Significant mismatch	Prioritise action

These bands are illustrative only. In future deployment, thresholds should be calibrated empirically rather than treated as universal cut-offs.

4.4.5 Why Gap Scores Matter

Gap scores are intended as diagnostic signals rather than performance league tables. For example:

- a high gap in Technology Characteristics \times Task level may suggest usability or interface design friction.
- a high gap in Implementation & Coordination Capacity \times Department level may suggest weak local support or coordination.
- a high gap in Trust, Safety & Governance \times Organisation level may indicate uncertainty around accountability, legitimacy, or data use.

The meaning of any score therefore depends on its position within the analytical matrix.

4.5 Additional Diagnostic Indicators

Gap magnitude alone does not explain why misalignment occurs. The Index therefore incorporates supplementary indicators.

4.5.1 Variation in Intended Affordances

If implementation actors disagree strongly about what the technology is meant to achieve, then observed gaps may partly reflect unclear expectations rather than implementation failure. Dispersion among intended-affordance respondents (for example, interquartile range or standard deviation) can therefore be treated as a diagnostic signal (Chan, 1998; LeBreton & Senter, 2008).

- High gap + low disagreement = shared vision, weak delivery
- High gap + high disagreement = contested or unclear expectations

- Low gap + high disagreement = possible local adaptation despite unclear intent.
- Low gap + low disagreement = shared vision and successful implementation

4.5.2 Variation in Actual Affordances

Differences across end users may indicate uneven implementation. Examples include:

- one profession benefits while another experiences burden.
- one department uses the tool effectively while another struggles.
- experienced staff adapt more easily than new users.

4.5.3 Missingness and “Not Applicable/Don’t Know”

These responses should not automatically be treated as error. They may indicate:

- limited visibility of organisational processes.
- unclear responsibilities.
- irrelevance of a technology to certain roles.
- insufficient communication or training.

Patterns of non-response should therefore be analysed alongside substantive scores.

4.6 Index Outputs

The Human-Tech Index is intended to generate outputs understandable to decision-makers, implementation teams, and researchers. All outputs remain traceable to item-level responses, allowing drill-down from summary patterns to specific survey items.

4.6.1 Quick Scan Outputs

The Quick Scan may produce (Figure 6):

- overall summary indicators.
- factor profiles.
- system-level profiles.
- a 5 × 5 matrix of gap scores.
- heatmaps or traffic-light visualisations.
- subgroup comparisons where relevant.

Level	Status
Task	Red
Role	Yellow
Team	Green
Department	Yellow
Organisation	Green

Figure 6. Example of traffic-light visualisation

Its main function is to identify where deeper investigation is warranted.

4.6.2 Deep Dive Outputs

The Deep Dive may produce (Figure 7):

- component-level diagnostic scores.
- ranked areas of concern.
- cross-level patterns.
- evidence tables linking issues to specific mechanisms.
- targeted intervention priorities.

Figure 7. Example of component-level diagnostic scores

Its function is diagnostic, enabling a more detailed understanding of what observed gap consists of.

5 Methodological Considerations and Limitations

This section sets out the methodological boundaries of the current framework and identifies priorities for further empirical development. The present deliverable introduces the conceptual architecture of the Human-Tech Index and an evidence-informed prototype assessment framework. It is not yet intended as a fully validated final instrument for operational deployment. Several considerations therefore merit attention.

5.1 Current Scope of Evidence Base

The Index has been developed primarily from:

- a structured review of published evidence relating to digital technology implementation in hospital settings.
- WP2 empirical case evidence generated in hospitals.

This combined foundation provides strong contextual relevance for hospital organisations and supports the use of healthcare as an analytically rich test environment. At the same time, the current evidence base is sector specific. Although the underlying logic of intended versus actual affordances may be transferable, wider applicability should be tested empirically in other sectors, technologies, and organisational settings.

5.2 Measurement Validation Still Required

Further development should include formal assessment of the measurement properties of the Index. Priority areas include:

- cognitive testing of survey items.
- reliability assessment.
- construct validation.
- sensitivity testing.
- longitudinal responsiveness testing.
- cross-context comparison.

A particular priority concerns the Quick Scan. Because each Quick Scan item represents a full factor within a single factor \times level cell, while using wording informed by the most salient underlying component(s), empirical testing is needed to confirm that respondents interpret the item as reflecting the broader factor rather than only the examples named in the wording.

For this reason, piloting should include cognitive interviews or think-aloud testing that explores how respondents understand each Quick Scan item, what they believe it refers to, and whether illustrative component wording helps or constrains interpretation. Findings from this stage may inform minor wording refinements or adjustment of examples used in specific cells, while preserving the overall 5×5 matrix structure.

These activities belong to the next practical development phase of the TechConnect project.

5.3 Interpretive Limits of Survey Data

The Index captures stakeholder perceptions of intended and actual affordances rather than direct technical performance metrics. This is deliberate, since many implementation challenges arise through perceived usefulness, trust, fit with workflows, and organisational workability rather than through technical functionality alone.

However, perception-based data also have limits. Responses may be shaped by local expectations, recent experiences, professional roles, or organisational climate. Survey findings should therefore be interpreted as indicators of socio-technical alignment rather than as standalone measures of technical effectiveness. Where possible, future applications may benefit from triangulation with operational indicators, usage data, or qualitative follow-up.

5.4 Equal Weighting

At the present stage, all factors, system levels, and components are treated with equal analytical importance. No differential weighting scheme is imposed at this point. This avoids introducing unsupported assumptions about the relative importance of particular dimensions before empirical testing.

Future research may show that some dimensions are more predictive of successful implementation than others, or that weighting should vary across technologies, organisational settings, or implementation phases. Until such evidence is available, equal weighting provides the more transparent and methodologically defensible starting point.

6 Conclusion

This deliverable has introduced the Human-Tech Skill Complementarity Index (Human-Tech Index) as a structured framework for assessing alignment between what digital technologies are expected to achieve and what they actually enable in practice.

Its central contribution is conceptual. The Index reframes implementation challenges not simply as adoption failures or technical shortcomings, but as affordance gaps emerging through the interaction of technologies, professional work practices, organisational arrangements, and governance conditions.

By combining a multi-source survey design, a multi-level analytical structure, and a two-stage diagnostic logic of Quick Scan and Deep Dive, the Index provides a coherent basis for future practical measurement and organisational learning.

Although the present framework is grounded empirically in healthcare settings, the underlying logic is not sector specific. The challenge of aligning intended, and actual technology affordances is relevant across many domains undergoing digital transformation. The next stages should focus on piloting, empirical validation and adaptation across contexts. With such development, the Human-Tech Index has the potential to provide organisations with a systematic and actionable means of diagnosing misalignment between technology intentions and real-world work practices, thereby supporting more effective human-technology complementarity in complex organisational environments.

By shifting attention from technology adoption alone to the quality of alignment between digital tools and real work systems, the Human-Tech Index offers a novel basis for evidence-informed digital transformation. Following empirical validation, it has the potential to support organisations in diagnosing misalignment early, prioritising corrective action, and improving the social and productive returns of technological investment. In this way, it contributes to a more system-oriented and outcome-focused approach to digital transformation.

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APPENDIX 1: QUICK SCAN FOR TECH SELECTION & IMPLEMENTATION PANEL

Human-Tech Index: Quick Scan

Tech Selection & Implementation Panel · Intended Affordance ratings

Technology being assessed: _____	Organisation / _____	Site: _____	Date: _____
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SECTION 1 — BACKGROUND

ID	Question	Response options (circle one)
BG-001	What is your age group?	Under 25 / 25–34 / 35–44 / 45–54 / 55–64 / 65 or older
BG-002	What is your gender?	Female / Male / Non-binary / Prefer not to say
BG-003	What is your highest level of education?	Secondary school / Vocational / Bachelor's / Master's / Doctoral / Other
BG-004	What is your primary professional role?
BG-009	Which department or unit do you primarily work in?
BG-013	Were you involved in the decision to adopt or configure this technology?	Yes, directly involved / Somewhat involved / Not involved

SECTION 2 — QUICK SCAN

The following questions ask about how the technology was intended to function when it was introduced. Please indicate to what extent each statement reflects what should be in place for the technology to function effectively.

Response scale: 1 = To a very low extent | 2 = To a small extent | 3 = To a moderate extent | 4 = To a large extent | 5 = To a very large extent | N/A = Not applicable / Don't know

Task level

The following questions refer to how the technology was intended to support specific tasks in day-to-day work. Based on the purpose for which this technology was introduced...

ID	Question	Rating (circle one)
QS-001	To what extent do you expect the technology to be useful and easy to use when people carry out everyday work tasks?	1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5 <input type="checkbox"/> N/A <input type="checkbox"/>
QS-002	To what extent do you expect the technology to fit the workflow and routines of everyday work tasks?	1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5 <input type="checkbox"/> N/A <input type="checkbox"/>
QS-003	To what extent do you expect people to be able to rely on the technology's outputs when carrying out everyday work tasks?	1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5 <input type="checkbox"/> N/A <input type="checkbox"/>
QS-004	To what extent do you expect adequate guidance and support to be available when people need to use the technology in everyday work tasks?	1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5 <input type="checkbox"/> N/A <input type="checkbox"/>

QS-005	To what extent do you expect the equipment and practical resources needed to use the technology to be available when people carry out everyday work tasks?	1 <input type="checkbox"/>	2 <input type="checkbox"/>	3 <input type="checkbox"/>	4 <input type="checkbox"/>	5 <input type="checkbox"/>	N/A <input type="checkbox"/>
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Role level

The following questions refer to how the technology was intended to support professional roles and responsibilities. Based on the purpose for which this technology was introduced...

ID	Question	Rating (circle one)					
QS-006	To what extent do you expect the technology to be useful for what the professional roles that use it are expected to accomplish?	1 <input type="checkbox"/>	2 <input type="checkbox"/>	3 <input type="checkbox"/>	4 <input type="checkbox"/>	5 <input type="checkbox"/>	N/A <input type="checkbox"/>
QS-007	To what extent do you expect the technology to fit the responsibilities and workload of the professional roles that use it?	1 <input type="checkbox"/>	2 <input type="checkbox"/>	3 <input type="checkbox"/>	4 <input type="checkbox"/>	5 <input type="checkbox"/>	N/A <input type="checkbox"/>
QS-008	To what extent do you expect it to be clear how the technology reaches its outputs and who is accountable for them in the professional roles that use it?	1 <input type="checkbox"/>	2 <input type="checkbox"/>	3 <input type="checkbox"/>	4 <input type="checkbox"/>	5 <input type="checkbox"/>	N/A <input type="checkbox"/>
QS-009	To what extent do you expect there to be adequate training, support and peer encouragement for the professional roles that use the technology to use it well?	1 <input type="checkbox"/>	2 <input type="checkbox"/>	3 <input type="checkbox"/>	4 <input type="checkbox"/>	5 <input type="checkbox"/>	N/A <input type="checkbox"/>
QS-010	To what extent do you expect the professional roles that use the technology to have the practical resources (equipment, staffing, time) they need?	1 <input type="checkbox"/>	2 <input type="checkbox"/>	3 <input type="checkbox"/>	4 <input type="checkbox"/>	5 <input type="checkbox"/>	N/A <input type="checkbox"/>

Team level

The following questions refer to how the technology was intended to support team-based work and collaboration. Based on the purpose for which this technology was introduced...

ID	Question	Rating (circle one)					
QS-011	To what extent do you expect the technology to work well with the other tools the team relies on?	1 <input type="checkbox"/>	2 <input type="checkbox"/>	3 <input type="checkbox"/>	4 <input type="checkbox"/>	5 <input type="checkbox"/>	N/A <input type="checkbox"/>
QS-012	To what extent do you expect the technology to fit the way the team will collaborate and coordinate its work?	1 <input type="checkbox"/>	2 <input type="checkbox"/>	3 <input type="checkbox"/>	4 <input type="checkbox"/>	5 <input type="checkbox"/>	N/A <input type="checkbox"/>
QS-013	To what extent do you expect the technology to be safe and reliable in the information the team shares and acts on?	1 <input type="checkbox"/>	2 <input type="checkbox"/>	3 <input type="checkbox"/>	4 <input type="checkbox"/>	5 <input type="checkbox"/>	N/A <input type="checkbox"/>
QS-014	To what extent do you expect the team to be supported and encouraged to use the technology well?	1 <input type="checkbox"/>	2 <input type="checkbox"/>	3 <input type="checkbox"/>	4 <input type="checkbox"/>	5 <input type="checkbox"/>	N/A <input type="checkbox"/>
QS-015	To what extent do you expect funding and practical resources to be sufficient for the team to use the technology?	1 <input type="checkbox"/>	2 <input type="checkbox"/>	3 <input type="checkbox"/>	4 <input type="checkbox"/>	5 <input type="checkbox"/>	N/A <input type="checkbox"/>

Department level

The following questions refer to how the technology was intended to be implemented and used within departments or units. Based on the purpose for which this technology was introduced...

ID	Question	Rating (circle one)					
QS-016	To what extent do you expect the technology to be useful for, and compatible with, the systems the department or unit will rely on to deliver its services?	1 <input type="checkbox"/>	2 <input type="checkbox"/>	3 <input type="checkbox"/>	4 <input type="checkbox"/>	5 <input type="checkbox"/>	N/A <input type="checkbox"/>
QS-017	To what extent do you expect the technology to fit the workflows and division of responsibilities within the department or unit?	1 <input type="checkbox"/>	2 <input type="checkbox"/>	3 <input type="checkbox"/>	4 <input type="checkbox"/>	5 <input type="checkbox"/>	N/A <input type="checkbox"/>

QS-018	To what extent do you expect the technology to function safely and reliably across the activities of the department or unit?	1 <input type="checkbox"/>	2 <input type="checkbox"/>	3 <input type="checkbox"/>	4 <input type="checkbox"/>	5 <input type="checkbox"/>	N/A <input type="checkbox"/>
QS-019	To what extent do you expect the department or unit to be ready, willing and supported by local leadership to embed the technology?	1 <input type="checkbox"/>	2 <input type="checkbox"/>	3 <input type="checkbox"/>	4 <input type="checkbox"/>	5 <input type="checkbox"/>	N/A <input type="checkbox"/>
QS-020	To what extent do you expect funding and infrastructure to be sufficient for the department or unit to use the technology?	1 <input type="checkbox"/>	2 <input type="checkbox"/>	3 <input type="checkbox"/>	4 <input type="checkbox"/>	5 <input type="checkbox"/>	N/A <input type="checkbox"/>

Organisational level

The following questions refer to how the technology was intended to be supported and governed at the organisational level. Based on the purpose for which this technology was introduced...

ID	Question	Rating (circle one)					
QS-021	To what extent do you expect the technology to be useful for, and compatible with, the wider digital infrastructure of the organisation?	1 <input type="checkbox"/>	2 <input type="checkbox"/>	3 <input type="checkbox"/>	4 <input type="checkbox"/>	5 <input type="checkbox"/>	N/A <input type="checkbox"/>
QS-022	To what extent do you expect the technology to fit the way work is organised across the organisation?	1 <input type="checkbox"/>	2 <input type="checkbox"/>	3 <input type="checkbox"/>	4 <input type="checkbox"/>	5 <input type="checkbox"/>	N/A <input type="checkbox"/>
QS-023	To what extent do you expect the technology to be trustworthy in ethical, legal and governance terms at the organisational level?	1 <input type="checkbox"/>	2 <input type="checkbox"/>	3 <input type="checkbox"/>	4 <input type="checkbox"/>	5 <input type="checkbox"/>	N/A <input type="checkbox"/>
QS-024	To what extent do you expect the organisation as a whole to be ready, willing and actively committed to adopting the technology?	1 <input type="checkbox"/>	2 <input type="checkbox"/>	3 <input type="checkbox"/>	4 <input type="checkbox"/>	5 <input type="checkbox"/>	N/A <input type="checkbox"/>
QS-025	To what extent do you expect the organisation to provide the financial and infrastructural resources needed to sustain the technology?	1 <input type="checkbox"/>	2 <input type="checkbox"/>	3 <input type="checkbox"/>	4 <input type="checkbox"/>	5 <input type="checkbox"/>	N/A <input type="checkbox"/>

Thank you for completing this survey.

APPENDIX 2: QUICK SCAN FOR END USERS

Human-Tech Index: Quick Scan

End Users · Actual Affordance ratings

Technology being assessed: _____	Organisation / _____	Site: _____	Date: _____
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SECTION 1 — BACKGROUND

ID	Question	Response options (circle one)
BG-001	What is your age group?	Under 25 / 25–34 / 35–44 / 45–54 / 55–64 / 65 or older
BG-002	What is your gender?	Female / Male / Non-binary / Prefer not to say
BG-003	What is your highest level of education?	Secondary school / Vocational / Bachelor's / Master's / Doctoral / Other
BG-004	What is your primary professional role?	Open text _____
BG-005	How would you rate your overall confidence in using digital technology in your work?	1=Very low 2=Low 3=Moderate 4=High 5=Very high
BG-006	How much prior experience do you have with similar technologies?	None / Limited (<6 months) / Moderate (6 months–2 years) / Extensive (>2 years)
BG-007	How would you describe your general attitude toward new technology in the workplace?	1=Very negative 2=Somewhat negative 3=Neutral 4=Somewhat positive 5=Very positive
BG-008	To what extent do you feel concerned about the impact of this technology on your professional role?	1=Not at all ... 5=To a very large extent
BG-009	Which department or unit do you primarily work in?	Open text _____
BG-010	How long have you been employed in your current organisation?	<1 year / 1–3 years / 4–7 years / 8–15 years / >15 years
BG-011	How frequently do you use the technology being assessed?	Daily / Several times per week / Weekly / A few times per month / Rarely or never
BG-012	How long have you been using this specific technology?	Not yet started / <3 months / 3–6 months / 6–12 months / >1 year
BG-013	Were you involved in the decision to adopt or configure this technology?	Yes, directly involved / Somewhat involved / Not involved
BG-014	Have you received formal training on how to use this technology?	Yes, comprehensive / Yes, brief / No formal training / Offered but did not attend

SECTION 2 — QUICK SCAN

The following questions ask about your experience with the technology in your daily work. Please indicate to what extent each statement reflects your experience.

Response scale: 1 = To a very low extent | 2 = To a small extent | 3 = To a moderate extent | 4 = To a large extent | 5 = To a very large extent | N/A = Not applicable / Don't know

Task level

The following questions refer to how the technology supports specific tasks in your day-to-day work. In your experience...

ID	Question	Rating (circle one)
QS-001	To what extent is the technology useful and easy to use when carrying out your everyday work tasks?	1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5 <input type="checkbox"/> N/A <input type="checkbox"/>
QS-002	To what extent does the technology fit the workflow and routines of your everyday work tasks?	1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5 <input type="checkbox"/> N/A <input type="checkbox"/>
QS-003	To what extent can you rely on the technology's outputs when carrying out everyday work tasks?	1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5 <input type="checkbox"/> N/A <input type="checkbox"/>
QS-004	To what extent is there adequate guidance and support available when you need to use the technology in everyday work tasks?	1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5 <input type="checkbox"/> N/A <input type="checkbox"/>
QS-005	To what extent are the equipment and practical resources needed to use the technology available when you carry out your everyday work tasks?	1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5 <input type="checkbox"/> N/A <input type="checkbox"/>

Role level

The following questions refer to how the technology supports your professional role. In your experience...

ID	Question	Rating (circle one)
QS-006	To what extent is the technology useful for what your professional role is expected to accomplish?	1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5 <input type="checkbox"/> N/A <input type="checkbox"/>
QS-007	To what extent does the technology fit the responsibilities and workload of your professional role?	1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5 <input type="checkbox"/> N/A <input type="checkbox"/>
QS-008	To what extent is it clear how the technology reaches its outputs and who is accountable for them in your professional role?	1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5 <input type="checkbox"/> N/A <input type="checkbox"/>
QS-009	To what extent is there adequate training, support and peer encouragement for your professional role to use the technology well?	1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5 <input type="checkbox"/> N/A <input type="checkbox"/>
QS-010	To what extent does your professional role have the practical resources (equipment, staffing, time) it needs to use the technology?	1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5 <input type="checkbox"/> N/A <input type="checkbox"/>

Team level

The following questions refer to how the technology supports team-based work and collaboration. In your experience...

ID	Question	Rating (circle one)
QS-011	To what extent does the technology work well with the other tools your team relies on?	1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5 <input type="checkbox"/> N/A <input type="checkbox"/>
QS-012	To what extent does the technology fit the way your team collaborates and coordinates its work?	1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5 <input type="checkbox"/> N/A <input type="checkbox"/>
QS-013	To what extent is the technology safe and reliable in the information your team shares and acts on?	1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5 <input type="checkbox"/> N/A <input type="checkbox"/>
QS-014	To what extent is your team supported and encouraged to use the technology well?	1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5 <input type="checkbox"/> N/A <input type="checkbox"/>
QS-015	To what extent are funding and practical resources sufficient for your team to use the technology?	1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5 <input type="checkbox"/> N/A <input type="checkbox"/>

Department level

The following questions refer to how the technology is used and managed within your department or unit. In your experience...

ID	Question	Rating (circle one)
QS-016	To what extent is the technology useful for, and compatible with, the systems your department or unit relies on to deliver its services?	1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5 <input type="checkbox"/> N/A <input type="checkbox"/>
QS-017	To what extent does the technology fit the workflows and division of responsibilities within your department or unit?	1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5 <input type="checkbox"/> N/A <input type="checkbox"/>
QS-018	To what extent does the technology function safely and reliably across the activities of your department or unit?	1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5 <input type="checkbox"/> N/A <input type="checkbox"/>
QS-019	To what extent is your department or unit ready, willing and supported by local leadership to embed the technology?	1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5 <input type="checkbox"/> N/A <input type="checkbox"/>
QS-020	To what extent are funding and infrastructure sufficient for your department or unit to use the technology?	1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5 <input type="checkbox"/> N/A <input type="checkbox"/>

Organisational level

The following questions refer to how the technology is supported and governed at the organizational level. In your experience...

ID	Question	Rating (circle one)
QS-021	To what extent is the technology useful for, and compatible with, the wider digital infrastructure of your organisation?	1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5 <input type="checkbox"/> N/A <input type="checkbox"/>
QS-022	To what extent does the technology fit the way work is organised across your organisation?	1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5 <input type="checkbox"/> N/A <input type="checkbox"/>
QS-023	To what extent is the technology trustworthy in ethical, legal and governance terms at the organisational level?	1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5 <input type="checkbox"/> N/A <input type="checkbox"/>
QS-024	To what extent is the organisation as a whole ready, willing, and actively committed to adopting the technology?	1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5 <input type="checkbox"/> N/A <input type="checkbox"/>
QS-025	To what extent does your organisation provide the financial and infrastructural resources needed to sustain the technology?	1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5 <input type="checkbox"/> N/A <input type="checkbox"/>

Thank you for completing this survey.

APPENDIX 3: DEEP DIVE FOR QUICK SCAN FOR TECH SELECTION & IMPLEMENTATION PANEL

Human-Tech Index: Deep Dive

Tech Selection & Implementation Panel · Intended Affordance ratings

Technology being assessed:	Organisation /	Site:	Date:
_____	_____	_____	_____

SECTION 1 — BACKGROUND

ID	Question	Rating (1–5 / N/A)
BG-001	What is your age group?	Under 25 / 25–34 / 35–44 / 45–54 / 55–64 / 65 or older
BG-002	What is your gender?	Female / Male / Non-binary / Prefer not to say
BG-003	What is your highest level of education?	Secondary school / Vocational / Bachelor's / Master's / Doctoral / Other
BG-004	What is your primary professional role?
BG-009	Which department or unit do you primarily work in?
BG-013	Were you involved in the decision to adopt or configure this technology?	Yes, directly involved / Somewhat involved / Not involved

SECTION 2 — DEEP DIVE

The following questions ask about how the technology was intended to function when it was introduced. Please indicate to what extent each statement reflects what should be in place for the technology to function effectively.

Response scale: 1 = To a very low extent | 2 = To a small extent | 3 = To a moderate extent | 4 = To a large extent | 5 = To a very large extent | N/A = Not applicable / Don't know

Task level

The following questions refer to how the technology is intended to support specific tasks in day-to-day work. Based on the purpose for which this technology was introduced...

ID	Question	Rating (1–5 / N/A)
DD-001	To what extent do you expect the technology to be intuitive and easy to use when people carry out everyday work tasks?	1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5 <input type="checkbox"/> N/A <input type="checkbox"/>
DD-002	To what extent do you expect the technology to be useful and valuable for achieving what everyday work tasks require?	1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5 <input type="checkbox"/> N/A <input type="checkbox"/>
DD-003	To what extent do you expect the technology to be compatible and interoperable with the other tools and data people rely on to complete everyday work tasks?	1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5 <input type="checkbox"/> N/A <input type="checkbox"/>
DD-004	To what extent do you expect the technology to fit within the workflows and routines people follow when completing everyday work tasks?	1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5 <input type="checkbox"/> N/A <input type="checkbox"/>
DD-005	To what extent do you expect the technology to reduce effort and mental load when people carry out everyday work tasks?	1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5 <input type="checkbox"/> N/A <input type="checkbox"/>
DD-006	To what extent do you expect the technology to support professional judgement and responsibility when people carry out everyday work tasks?	1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5 <input type="checkbox"/> N/A <input type="checkbox"/>
DD-007	To what extent do you expect the technology to improve the quality and efficiency of everyday work tasks?	1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5 <input type="checkbox"/> N/A <input type="checkbox"/>

DD-008	To what extent do you expect the technology to support coordination, communication, and shared understanding during everyday work tasks?	1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5 <input type="checkbox"/> N/A <input type="checkbox"/>
DD-009	To what extent do you expect the technology to be accurate, consistent, and free from bias in the outputs people rely on for everyday work tasks?	1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5 <input type="checkbox"/> N/A <input type="checkbox"/>
DD-010	To what extent do you expect the technology's outputs and reasoning to be clear and interpretable when people use it for everyday work tasks?	1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5 <input type="checkbox"/> N/A <input type="checkbox"/>
DD-011	To what extent do you expect the technology to function reliably and minimise errors and risks in everyday work tasks?	1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5 <input type="checkbox"/> N/A <input type="checkbox"/>
DD-012	To what extent do you expect the technology to be secure, ethical, and in line with regulations when people use it for everyday work tasks?	1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5 <input type="checkbox"/> N/A <input type="checkbox"/>
DD-013	To what extent do you expect it to be clear who is responsible and accountable when the technology is used for everyday work tasks?	1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5 <input type="checkbox"/> N/A <input type="checkbox"/>
DD-014	To what extent do you expect the organisation to be ready and willing to support people's use of the technology in everyday work tasks?	1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5 <input type="checkbox"/> N/A <input type="checkbox"/>
DD-015	To what extent do you expect there to be sufficient guidance, training, and technical support for using the technology in everyday work tasks?	1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5 <input type="checkbox"/> N/A <input type="checkbox"/>
DD-016	To what extent do you expect peer support and prevailing norms to encourage people to use the technology for everyday work tasks?	1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5 <input type="checkbox"/> N/A <input type="checkbox"/>
DD-017	To what extent do you expect sufficient funding to be in place for the technology to be used for everyday work tasks?	1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5 <input type="checkbox"/> N/A <input type="checkbox"/>
DD-018	To what extent do you expect sufficient infrastructure, equipment, and personnel to be in place for everyday work tasks that use the technology?	1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5 <input type="checkbox"/> N/A <input type="checkbox"/>

Role level

The following questions refer to how the technology is intended to support professional roles and responsibilities. Based on the purpose for which this technology was introduced...

ID	Question	Rating (1–5 / N/A)
DD-019	To what extent do you expect the technology to be intuitive and easy to use for the day-to-day demands of the professional roles that use it?	1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5 <input type="checkbox"/> N/A <input type="checkbox"/>
DD-020	To what extent do you expect the technology to be useful and valuable for what the professional roles using it are expected to accomplish?	1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5 <input type="checkbox"/> N/A <input type="checkbox"/>
DD-021	To what extent do you expect the technology to be compatible and interoperable with the other systems that the professional roles using it depend on?	1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5 <input type="checkbox"/> N/A <input type="checkbox"/>
DD-022	To what extent do you expect the technology to fit within the workflows and routines that the professional roles using it usually follow?	1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5 <input type="checkbox"/> N/A <input type="checkbox"/>
DD-023	To what extent do you expect the technology to reduce effort and mental load across the responsibilities of the professional roles using it?	1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5 <input type="checkbox"/> N/A <input type="checkbox"/>
DD-024	To what extent do you expect the technology to support professional judgement and responsibility in line with what the roles using it require?	1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5 <input type="checkbox"/> N/A <input type="checkbox"/>
DD-025	To what extent do you expect the technology to improve the quality and efficiency of the work the professional roles using it deliver?	1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5 <input type="checkbox"/> N/A <input type="checkbox"/>
DD-026	To what extent do you expect the technology to support coordination, communication, and shared understanding with the people the professional roles using it regularly work with?	1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5 <input type="checkbox"/> N/A <input type="checkbox"/>
DD-027	To what extent do you expect the technology to be accurate, consistent, and free from bias in the outputs the professional roles using it depend on?	1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5 <input type="checkbox"/> N/A <input type="checkbox"/>
DD-028	To what extent do you expect the technology's outputs and reasoning to be clear and interpretable for the decisions the professional roles using it are expected to make?	1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5 <input type="checkbox"/> N/A <input type="checkbox"/>

DD-029	To what extent do you expect the technology to function reliably and minimise errors and risks for the responsibilities the professional roles using it carry?	1□ 2□ 3□ 4□ 5□ N/A□
DD-030	To what extent do you expect the technology to be secure, ethical, and in line with regulations for the duties the professional roles using it hold?	1□ 2□ 3□ 4□ 5□ N/A□
DD-031	To what extent do you expect it to be clear who is responsible and accountable within the professional roles using the technology?	1□ 2□ 3□ 4□ 5□ N/A□
DD-032	To what extent do you expect the organisation to be ready and willing to support the professional roles adopting the technology?	1□ 2□ 3□ 4□ 5□ N/A□
DD-033	To what extent do you expect there to be sufficient guidance, training, and technical support for the professional roles using the technology to do so well?	1□ 2□ 3□ 4□ 5□ N/A□
DD-034	To what extent do you expect peer support and prevailing norms within professional roles to encourage use of the technology?	1□ 2□ 3□ 4□ 5□ N/A□
DD-035	To what extent do you expect sufficient funding to be available for the professional roles using the technology?	1□ 2□ 3□ 4□ 5□ N/A□
DD-036	To what extent do you expect sufficient infrastructure, equipment, and personnel to be in place for the professional roles using the technology?	1□ 2□ 3□ 4□ 5□ N/A□

Team level

The following questions refer to how the technology is intended to support team-based work and collaboration. Based on the purpose for which this technology was introduced...

ID	Question	Rating (1–5 / N/A)
DD-037	To what extent do you expect the technology to be intuitive and easy to use when teams work together?	1□ 2□ 3□ 4□ 5□ N/A□
DD-038	To what extent do you expect the technology to be useful and valuable for the work teams do together?	1□ 2□ 3□ 4□ 5□ N/A□
DD-039	To what extent do you expect the technology to be compatible and interoperable with the tools teams use to work together?	1□ 2□ 3□ 4□ 5□ N/A□
DD-040	To what extent do you expect the technology to fit within the workflows and routines teams use to coordinate their work?	1□ 2□ 3□ 4□ 5□ N/A□
DD-041	To what extent do you expect the technology to reduce effort and mental load on teams as a whole?	1□ 2□ 3□ 4□ 5□ N/A□
DD-042	To what extent do you expect the technology to support professional judgement and responsibility within teams?	1□ 2□ 3□ 4□ 5□ N/A□
DD-043	To what extent do you expect the technology to improve the quality and efficiency of the work teams do together?	1□ 2□ 3□ 4□ 5□ N/A□
DD-044	To what extent do you expect the technology to support coordination, communication, and shared understanding within teams?	1□ 2□ 3□ 4□ 5□ N/A□
DD-045	To what extent do you expect the technology to be accurate, consistent, and free from bias in the information teams share and act on?	1□ 2□ 3□ 4□ 5□ N/A□
DD-046	To what extent do you expect the technology's outputs and reasoning to be clear and interpretable to the members of teams that use it?	1□ 2□ 3□ 4□ 5□ N/A□
DD-047	To what extent do you expect the technology to function reliably and minimise errors and risks in the work teams do together?	1□ 2□ 3□ 4□ 5□ N/A□
DD-048	To what extent do you expect the technology to be secure, ethical, and in line with regulations in how teams share and handle information?	1□ 2□ 3□ 4□ 5□ N/A□
DD-049	To what extent do you expect it to be clear who is responsible and accountable within teams when outcomes involve the technology?	1□ 2□ 3□ 4□ 5□ N/A□
DD-050	To what extent do you expect the organisation to be ready and willing to support teams in taking up the technology?	1□ 2□ 3□ 4□ 5□ N/A□

DD-051	To what extent do you expect there to be sufficient guidance, training, and technical support for teams to use the technology well together?	1□ 2□ 3□ 4□ 5□ N/A□
DD-052	To what extent do you expect peer support and prevailing norms within teams to encourage use of the technology?	1□ 2□ 3□ 4□ 5□ N/A□
DD-053	To what extent do you expect sufficient funding to be available for teams to use the technology?	1□ 2□ 3□ 4□ 5□ N/A□
DD-054	To what extent do you expect sufficient infrastructure, equipment, and personnel to be in place for teams to use the technology?	1□ 2□ 3□ 4□ 5□ N/A□

Department/Unit level

The following questions refer to how the technology is intended to be implemented and used within departments or units. Think about the department's workflows, coordination, and local management of the technology. Based on the purpose for which this technology was introduced...

ID	Question	Rating (1–5 / N/A)
DD-055	To what extent do you expect the technology to be intuitive and easy to use across departments and units?	1□ 2□ 3□ 4□ 5□ N/A□
DD-056	To what extent do you expect the technology to be useful and valuable for what departments or units are there to deliver?	1□ 2□ 3□ 4□ 5□ N/A□
DD-057	To what extent do you expect the technology to be compatible and interoperable with the digital systems in place in departments or units?	1□ 2□ 3□ 4□ 5□ N/A□
DD-058	To what extent do you expect the technology to fit within the workflows and routines of departments or units?	1□ 2□ 3□ 4□ 5□ N/A□
DD-059	To what extent do you expect the technology to reduce effort and mental load on staff in departments or units?	1□ 2□ 3□ 4□ 5□ N/A□
DD-060	To what extent do you expect the technology to support professional judgement and responsibility across staff in departments or units?	1□ 2□ 3□ 4□ 5□ N/A□
DD-061	To what extent do you expect the technology to improve the quality and efficiency of the services departments or units deliver?	1□ 2□ 3□ 4□ 5□ N/A□
DD-062	To what extent do you expect the technology to support coordination, communication, and shared understanding across staff in departments or units?	1□ 2□ 3□ 4□ 5□ N/A□
DD-063	To what extent do you expect the technology to be accurate, consistent, and free from bias in the outputs used across departments or units?	1□ 2□ 3□ 4□ 5□ N/A□
DD-064	To what extent do you expect the technology's outputs and reasoning to be clear and interpretable to staff across departments or units?	1□ 2□ 3□ 4□ 5□ N/A□
DD-065	To what extent do you expect the technology to function reliably and minimise errors and risks across the activities of departments or units?	1□ 2□ 3□ 4□ 5□ N/A□
DD-066	To what extent do you expect the technology to be secure, ethical, and in line with regulations as it is managed in departments or units?	1□ 2□ 3□ 4□ 5□ N/A□
DD-067	To what extent do you expect it to be clear who is responsible and accountable within departments or units when outcomes involve the technology?	1□ 2□ 3□ 4□ 5□ N/A□
DD-068	To what extent do you expect the organisation to be ready and willing to support departments or units in embedding the technology?	1□ 2□ 3□ 4□ 5□ N/A□
DD-069	To what extent do you expect there to be sufficient guidance, training, and technical support for departments or units to use the technology well?	1□ 2□ 3□ 4□ 5□ N/A□
DD-070	To what extent do you expect peer support and prevailing norms within departments or units to encourage use of the technology?	1□ 2□ 3□ 4□ 5□ N/A□
DD-071	To what extent do you expect sufficient funding to be available for departments or units to use the technology?	1□ 2□ 3□ 4□ 5□ N/A□
DD-072	To what extent do you expect sufficient infrastructure, equipment, and personnel to be in place for departments or units to use the technology?	1□ 2□ 3□ 4□ 5□ N/A□

Organisational level

The following questions refer to how the technology is intended to be supported and governed at the organisational level. Think about the organisation's overall strategy, governance, and infrastructure for this technology. Based on the purpose for which this technology was introduced...

ID	Question	Rating (1–5 / N/A)
DD-073	To what extent do you expect the technology to be intuitive and easy to use for people across the organisation?	1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5 <input type="checkbox"/> N/A <input type="checkbox"/>
DD-074	To what extent do you expect the technology to be useful and valuable for what the organisation as a whole aims to achieve?	1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5 <input type="checkbox"/> N/A <input type="checkbox"/>
DD-075	To what extent do you expect the technology to be compatible and interoperable with the wider digital infrastructure of the organisation?	1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5 <input type="checkbox"/> N/A <input type="checkbox"/>
DD-076	To what extent do you expect the technology to fit within the workflows and routines that shape how work is organised across the organisation?	1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5 <input type="checkbox"/> N/A <input type="checkbox"/>
DD-077	To what extent do you expect the technology to reduce effort and mental load on the workforce across the organisation?	1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5 <input type="checkbox"/> N/A <input type="checkbox"/>
DD-078	To what extent do you expect the technology to support professional judgement and responsibility across the workforce of the organisation?	1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5 <input type="checkbox"/> N/A <input type="checkbox"/>
DD-079	To what extent do you expect the technology to improve the quality and efficiency of what the organisation delivers overall?	1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5 <input type="checkbox"/> N/A <input type="checkbox"/>
DD-080	To what extent do you expect the technology to support coordination, communication, and shared understanding across the organisation?	1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5 <input type="checkbox"/> N/A <input type="checkbox"/>
DD-081	To what extent do you expect the technology to be accurate, consistent, and free from bias in the outputs the organisation relies on overall?	1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5 <input type="checkbox"/> N/A <input type="checkbox"/>
DD-082	To what extent do you expect the technology's outputs and reasoning to be clear and interpretable to stakeholders across the organisation?	1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5 <input type="checkbox"/> N/A <input type="checkbox"/>
DD-083	To what extent do you expect the technology to function reliably and minimise errors and risks for the organisation as a whole?	1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5 <input type="checkbox"/> N/A <input type="checkbox"/>
DD-084	To what extent do you expect the technology to be secure, ethical, and in line with regulations in how the organisation governs it overall?	1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5 <input type="checkbox"/> N/A <input type="checkbox"/>
DD-085	To what extent do you expect it to be clear who is responsible and accountable at the organisational level for outcomes involving the technology?	1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5 <input type="checkbox"/> N/A <input type="checkbox"/>
DD-086	To what extent do you expect the organisation as a whole to be ready and willing to back adoption of the technology?	1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5 <input type="checkbox"/> N/A <input type="checkbox"/>
DD-087	To what extent do you expect there to be sufficient guidance, training, and technical support for the technology across the organisation?	1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5 <input type="checkbox"/> N/A <input type="checkbox"/>
DD-088	To what extent do you expect peer support and prevailing norms across the organisation to encourage use of the technology?	1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5 <input type="checkbox"/> N/A <input type="checkbox"/>
DD-089	To what extent do you expect sufficient funding to be allocated by the organisation for the technology overall?	1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5 <input type="checkbox"/> N/A <input type="checkbox"/>
DD-090	To what extent do you expect sufficient infrastructure, equipment, and personnel to be in place across the organisation to use the technology?	1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5 <input type="checkbox"/> N/A <input type="checkbox"/>

Thank you for completing this survey.

APPENDIX 4: DEEP DIVE FOR END USERS

Human-Tech Index: Deep Dive

End Users · Actual Affordance ratings

Technology being assessed:	Organisation /	Site:	Date:
_____	_____	_____	_____

SECTION 1 — BACKGROUND

ID	Question	Rating (1–5 / N/A)
BG-001	What is your age group?	Under 25 / 25–34 / 35–44 / 45–54 / 55–64 / 65 or older
BG-002	What is your gender?	Female / Male / Non-binary / Prefer not to say
BG-003	What is your highest level of education?	Secondary school / Vocational / Bachelor's / Master's / Doctoral / Other
BG-004	What is your primary professional role?	Open text _____
BG-005	How would you rate your overall confidence in using digital technology in your work?	1=Very low 2=Low 3=Moderate 4=High 5=Very high
BG-006	How much prior experience do you have with similar technologies?	None / Limited (<6 months) / Moderate (6 months–2 years) / Extensive (>2 years)
BG-007	How would you describe your general attitude toward new technology in the workplace?	1=Very negative 2=Somewhat negative 3=Neutral 4=Somewhat positive 5=Very positive
BG-008	To what extent do you feel concerned about the impact of this technology on your professional role?	1=Not at all ... 5=To a very large extent
BG-009	Which department or unit do you primarily work in?	Open text _____
BG-010	How long have you been employed in your current organisation?	<1 year / 1–3 years / 4–7 years / 8–15 years / >15 years
BG-011	How frequently do you use the technology being assessed?	Daily / Several times per week / Weekly / A few times per month / Rarely or never
BG-012	How long have you been using this specific technology?	Not yet started / <3 months / 3–6 months / 6–12 months / >1 year
BG-013	Were you involved in the decision to adopt or configure this technology?	Yes, directly involved / Somewhat involved / Not involved
BG-014	Have you received formal training on how to use this technology?	Yes, comprehensive / Yes, brief / No formal training / Offered but did not attend

SECTION 2 — DEEP DIVE

The following questions ask about your direct experience with the technology. Please indicate to what extent each statement reflects what you have experienced.

Response scale: 1 = To a very low extent | 2 = To a small extent | 3 = To a moderate extent | 4 = To a large extent | 5 = To a very large extent | N/A = Not applicable / Don't know

Task level

The following questions refer to how the technology supports specific tasks in your day-to-day work. In your experience...

ID	Question	Rating (1–5 / N/A)
DD-001	To what extent is the technology intuitive and easy to use when you carry out everyday work tasks?	1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5 <input type="checkbox"/> N/A <input type="checkbox"/>
DD-002	To what extent is the technology useful and valuable for achieving what your everyday work tasks require?	1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5 <input type="checkbox"/> N/A <input type="checkbox"/>
DD-003	To what extent is the technology compatible and interoperable with the other tools and data you rely on to complete everyday work tasks?	1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5 <input type="checkbox"/> N/A <input type="checkbox"/>
DD-004	To what extent does the technology fit within the workflows and routines you follow when completing everyday work tasks?	1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5 <input type="checkbox"/> N/A <input type="checkbox"/>
DD-005	To what extent does the technology reduce effort and mental load when you carry out everyday work tasks?	1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5 <input type="checkbox"/> N/A <input type="checkbox"/>
DD-006	To what extent does the technology support professional judgement and responsibility when you carry out everyday work tasks?	1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5 <input type="checkbox"/> N/A <input type="checkbox"/>
DD-007	To what extent does the technology improve the quality and efficiency of your everyday work tasks?	1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5 <input type="checkbox"/> N/A <input type="checkbox"/>
DD-008	To what extent does the technology support coordination, communication, and shared understanding during your everyday work tasks?	1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5 <input type="checkbox"/> N/A <input type="checkbox"/>
DD-009	To what extent is the technology accurate, consistent, and free from bias in the outputs you rely on for everyday work tasks?	1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5 <input type="checkbox"/> N/A <input type="checkbox"/>
DD-010	To what extent are the technology's outputs and reasoning clear and interpretable when you use it for everyday work tasks?	1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5 <input type="checkbox"/> N/A <input type="checkbox"/>
DD-011	To what extent does the technology function reliably and minimise errors and risks in your everyday work tasks?	1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5 <input type="checkbox"/> N/A <input type="checkbox"/>
DD-012	To what extent is the technology secure, ethical, and in line with regulations when you use it for everyday work tasks?	1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5 <input type="checkbox"/> N/A <input type="checkbox"/>
DD-013	To what extent is it clear who is responsible and accountable when the technology is used for your everyday work tasks?	1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5 <input type="checkbox"/> N/A <input type="checkbox"/>
DD-014	To what extent is the organisation ready and willing to support your use of the technology in everyday work tasks?	1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5 <input type="checkbox"/> N/A <input type="checkbox"/>
DD-015	To what extent is there sufficient guidance, training, and technical support for using the technology in your everyday work tasks?	1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5 <input type="checkbox"/> N/A <input type="checkbox"/>
DD-016	To what extent do peer support and prevailing norms encourage you to use the technology for your everyday work tasks?	1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5 <input type="checkbox"/> N/A <input type="checkbox"/>
DD-017	To what extent is sufficient funding in place for the technology to be used for your everyday work tasks?	1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5 <input type="checkbox"/> N/A <input type="checkbox"/>
DD-018	To what extent is sufficient infrastructure, equipment, and personnel in place for your everyday work tasks that use the technology?	1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5 <input type="checkbox"/> N/A <input type="checkbox"/>

Role level

The following questions refer to how the technology supports your professional role and responsibilities. In your experience...

ID	Question	Rating (1–5 / N/A)
DD-019	To what extent is the technology intuitive and easy to use for the day-to-day demands of your professional role?	1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5 <input type="checkbox"/> N/A <input type="checkbox"/>
DD-020	To what extent is the technology useful and valuable for what your professional role is expected to accomplish?	1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5 <input type="checkbox"/> N/A <input type="checkbox"/>
DD-021	To what extent is the technology compatible and interoperable with the other systems your professional role depends on?	1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5 <input type="checkbox"/> N/A <input type="checkbox"/>

DD-022	To what extent does the technology fit within the workflows and routines that your professional role usually follows?	1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5 <input type="checkbox"/> N/A <input type="checkbox"/>
DD-023	To what extent does the technology reduce effort and mental load across the responsibilities of your professional role?	1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5 <input type="checkbox"/> N/A <input type="checkbox"/>
DD-024	To what extent does the technology support professional judgement and responsibility in line with what your role requires?	1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5 <input type="checkbox"/> N/A <input type="checkbox"/>
DD-025	To what extent does the technology improve the quality and efficiency of the work your professional role delivers?	1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5 <input type="checkbox"/> N/A <input type="checkbox"/>
DD-026	To what extent does the technology support coordination, communication, and shared understanding with the people your professional role regularly works with?	1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5 <input type="checkbox"/> N/A <input type="checkbox"/>
DD-027	To what extent is the technology accurate, consistent, and free from bias in the outputs your professional role depends on?	1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5 <input type="checkbox"/> N/A <input type="checkbox"/>
DD-028	To what extent are the technology's outputs and reasoning clear and interpretable for the decisions your professional role is expected to make?	1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5 <input type="checkbox"/> N/A <input type="checkbox"/>
DD-029	To what extent does the technology function reliably and minimise errors and risks for the responsibilities your professional role carries?	1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5 <input type="checkbox"/> N/A <input type="checkbox"/>
DD-030	To what extent is the technology secure, ethical, and in line with regulations for the duties your professional role holds?	1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5 <input type="checkbox"/> N/A <input type="checkbox"/>
DD-031	To what extent is it clear who is responsible and accountable within your professional role when the technology is used?	1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5 <input type="checkbox"/> N/A <input type="checkbox"/>
DD-032	To what extent is the organisation ready and willing to support your professional role in adopting the technology?	1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5 <input type="checkbox"/> N/A <input type="checkbox"/>
DD-033	To what extent is there sufficient guidance, training, and technical support for your professional role to use the technology well?	1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5 <input type="checkbox"/> N/A <input type="checkbox"/>
DD-034	To what extent do peer support and prevailing norms within your professional role encourage use of the technology?	1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5 <input type="checkbox"/> N/A <input type="checkbox"/>
DD-035	To what extent is sufficient funding available for your professional role to make use of the technology?	1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5 <input type="checkbox"/> N/A <input type="checkbox"/>
DD-036	To what extent is sufficient infrastructure, equipment, and personnel in place for your professional role to use the technology?	1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5 <input type="checkbox"/> N/A <input type="checkbox"/>

Team level

The following questions refer to how the technology supports team-based work and collaboration. In your experience...

ID	Question	Rating (1–5 / N/A)
DD-037	To what extent is the technology intuitive and easy to use when your team works together?	1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5 <input type="checkbox"/> N/A <input type="checkbox"/>
DD-038	To what extent is the technology useful and valuable for the work your team does together?	1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5 <input type="checkbox"/> N/A <input type="checkbox"/>
DD-039	To what extent is the technology compatible and interoperable with the tools your team uses to work together?	1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5 <input type="checkbox"/> N/A <input type="checkbox"/>
DD-040	To what extent does the technology fit within the workflows and routines your team uses to coordinate its work?	1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5 <input type="checkbox"/> N/A <input type="checkbox"/>
DD-041	To what extent does the technology reduce effort and mental load on your team as a whole?	1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5 <input type="checkbox"/> N/A <input type="checkbox"/>
DD-042	To what extent does the technology support professional judgement and responsibility within your team?	1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5 <input type="checkbox"/> N/A <input type="checkbox"/>
DD-043	To what extent does the technology improve the quality and efficiency of the work your team does together?	1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5 <input type="checkbox"/> N/A <input type="checkbox"/>

DD-044	To what extent does the technology support coordination, communication, and shared understanding within your team?	1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5 <input type="checkbox"/> N/A <input type="checkbox"/>
DD-045	To what extent is the technology accurate, consistent, and free from bias in the information your team shares and acts on?	1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5 <input type="checkbox"/> N/A <input type="checkbox"/>
DD-046	To what extent are the technology's outputs and reasoning clear and interpretable to the members of your team?	1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5 <input type="checkbox"/> N/A <input type="checkbox"/>
DD-047	To what extent does the technology function reliably and minimise errors and risks in the work your team does together?	1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5 <input type="checkbox"/> N/A <input type="checkbox"/>
DD-048	To what extent is the technology secure, ethical, and in line with regulations in how your team shares and handles information?	1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5 <input type="checkbox"/> N/A <input type="checkbox"/>
DD-049	To what extent is it clear who is responsible and accountable within your team when outcomes involve the technology?	1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5 <input type="checkbox"/> N/A <input type="checkbox"/>
DD-050	To what extent is the organisation ready and willing to support your team in taking up the technology?	1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5 <input type="checkbox"/> N/A <input type="checkbox"/>
DD-051	To what extent is there sufficient guidance, training, and technical support for your team to use the technology well together?	1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5 <input type="checkbox"/> N/A <input type="checkbox"/>
DD-052	To what extent do peer support and prevailing norms within your team encourage use of the technology?	1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5 <input type="checkbox"/> N/A <input type="checkbox"/>
DD-053	To what extent is sufficient funding available for your team to use the technology?	1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5 <input type="checkbox"/> N/A <input type="checkbox"/>
DD-054	To what extent is sufficient infrastructure, equipment, and personnel in place for your team to use the technology?	1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5 <input type="checkbox"/> N/A <input type="checkbox"/>

Department/Unit level

The following questions refer to how the technology is used and managed within your department or unit. In your experience...

ID	Question	Rating (1–5 / N/A)
DD-055	To what extent is the technology intuitive and easy to use across your department or unit?	1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5 <input type="checkbox"/> N/A <input type="checkbox"/>
DD-056	To what extent is the technology useful and valuable for what your department or unit is there to deliver?	1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5 <input type="checkbox"/> N/A <input type="checkbox"/>
DD-057	To what extent is the technology compatible and interoperable with the digital systems in place in your department or unit?	1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5 <input type="checkbox"/> N/A <input type="checkbox"/>
DD-058	To what extent does the technology fit within the workflows and routines of your department or unit?	1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5 <input type="checkbox"/> N/A <input type="checkbox"/>
DD-059	To what extent does the technology reduce effort and mental load on staff in your department or unit?	1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5 <input type="checkbox"/> N/A <input type="checkbox"/>
DD-060	To what extent does the technology support professional judgement and responsibility across staff in your department or unit?	1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5 <input type="checkbox"/> N/A <input type="checkbox"/>
DD-061	To what extent does the technology improve the quality and efficiency of the services your department or unit delivers?	1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5 <input type="checkbox"/> N/A <input type="checkbox"/>
DD-062	To what extent does the technology support coordination, communication, and shared understanding across staff in your department or unit?	1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5 <input type="checkbox"/> N/A <input type="checkbox"/>
DD-063	To what extent is the technology accurate, consistent, and free from bias in the outputs used across your department or unit?	1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5 <input type="checkbox"/> N/A <input type="checkbox"/>
DD-064	To what extent are the technology's outputs and reasoning clear and interpretable to staff across your department or unit?	1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5 <input type="checkbox"/> N/A <input type="checkbox"/>
DD-065	To what extent does the technology function reliably and minimise errors and risks across the activities of your department or unit?	1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5 <input type="checkbox"/> N/A <input type="checkbox"/>

DD-066	To what extent is the technology secure, ethical, and in line with regulations as it is managed in your department or unit?	1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5 <input type="checkbox"/> N/A <input type="checkbox"/>
DD-067	To what extent is it clear who is responsible and accountable within your department or unit when outcomes involve the technology?	1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5 <input type="checkbox"/> N/A <input type="checkbox"/>
DD-068	To what extent is the organisation ready and willing to support your department or unit in embedding the technology?	1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5 <input type="checkbox"/> N/A <input type="checkbox"/>
DD-069	To what extent is there sufficient guidance, training, and technical support for your department or unit to use the technology well?	1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5 <input type="checkbox"/> N/A <input type="checkbox"/>
DD-070	To what extent do peer support and prevailing norms within your department or unit encourage use of the technology?	1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5 <input type="checkbox"/> N/A <input type="checkbox"/>
DD-071	To what extent is sufficient funding available for your department or unit to use the technology?	1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5 <input type="checkbox"/> N/A <input type="checkbox"/>
DD-072	To what extent is sufficient infrastructure, equipment, and personnel in place for your department or unit to use the technology?	1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5 <input type="checkbox"/> N/A <input type="checkbox"/>

Organisational level

The following questions refer to how the technology is supported and governed at the organisational level. In your experience...

ID	Question	Rating (1–5 / N/A)
DD-073	To what extent is the technology intuitive and easy to use for people across your organisation?	1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5 <input type="checkbox"/> N/A <input type="checkbox"/>
DD-074	To what extent is the technology useful and valuable for what your organisation as a whole aims to achieve?	1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5 <input type="checkbox"/> N/A <input type="checkbox"/>
DD-075	To what extent is the technology compatible and interoperable with the wider digital infrastructure of your organisation?	1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5 <input type="checkbox"/> N/A <input type="checkbox"/>
DD-076	To what extent does the technology fit within the workflows and routines that shape how work is organised across your organisation?	1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5 <input type="checkbox"/> N/A <input type="checkbox"/>
DD-077	To what extent does the technology reduce effort and mental load on the workforce across your organisation?	1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5 <input type="checkbox"/> N/A <input type="checkbox"/>
DD-078	To what extent does the technology support professional judgement and responsibility across the workforce of your organisation?	1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5 <input type="checkbox"/> N/A <input type="checkbox"/>
DD-079	To what extent does the technology improve the quality and efficiency of what your organisation delivers overall?	1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5 <input type="checkbox"/> N/A <input type="checkbox"/>
DD-080	To what extent does the technology support coordination, communication, and shared understanding across your organisation?	1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5 <input type="checkbox"/> N/A <input type="checkbox"/>
DD-081	To what extent is the technology accurate, consistent, and free from bias in the outputs your organisation relies on overall?	1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5 <input type="checkbox"/> N/A <input type="checkbox"/>
DD-082	To what extent are the technology's outputs and reasoning clear and interpretable to stakeholders across your organisation?	1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5 <input type="checkbox"/> N/A <input type="checkbox"/>
DD-083	To what extent does the technology function reliably and minimise errors and risks for your organisation as a whole?	1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5 <input type="checkbox"/> N/A <input type="checkbox"/>
DD-084	To what extent is the technology secure, ethical, and in line with regulations in how your organisation governs it overall?	1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5 <input type="checkbox"/> N/A <input type="checkbox"/>
DD-085	To what extent is it clear who is responsible and accountable at the organisational level for outcomes involving the technology?	1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5 <input type="checkbox"/> N/A <input type="checkbox"/>
DD-086	To what extent is the organisation as a whole ready and willing to back adoption of the technology?	1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5 <input type="checkbox"/> N/A <input type="checkbox"/>
DD-087	To what extent is there sufficient guidance, training, and technical support for the technology across your organisation?	1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5 <input type="checkbox"/> N/A <input type="checkbox"/>

DD-088	To what extent do peer support and prevailing norms across your organisation encourage use of the technology?	1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5 <input type="checkbox"/> N/A <input type="checkbox"/>
DD-089	To what extent is sufficient funding allocated by your organisation for the technology overall?	1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5 <input type="checkbox"/> N/A <input type="checkbox"/>
DD-090	To what extent is sufficient infrastructure, equipment, and personnel in place across your organisation to use the technology?	1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5 <input type="checkbox"/> N/A <input type="checkbox"/>

Thank you for completing this survey.